

6-23-2024

Genocide Memorialization through Law in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Reconciling the Irreconcilable?

Carna Pistan

Institute for Comparative Federalism, Eurac Research

Follow this and additional works at: <https://digitalcommons.usf.edu/gsp>

Recommended Citation

Pistan, Carna (2024) "Genocide Memorialization through Law in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Reconciling the Irreconcilable?," *Genocide Studies and Prevention: An International Journal*: Vol. 17: Iss. 3: 1–25.

DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.5038/1911-9933.17.3.1950>

Available at: <https://digitalcommons.usf.edu/gsp/vol17/iss3/3>

This Article is brought to you for free and open access by the Open Access Journals at Digital Commons @ University of South Florida. It has been accepted for inclusion in *Genocide Studies and Prevention: An International Journal* by an authorized editor of Digital Commons @ University of South Florida. For more information, please contact digitalcommons@usf.edu.

Genocide Memorialization through Law in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Reconciling the Irreconcilable?

Acknowledgements

I sincerely thank the editor and reviewers for taking the time to review my manuscript and providing constructive feedback to improve the manuscript. This publication is part of the project We-R (Illusions of eternity: the Constitution as a lieu de mémoire and the problem of collective remembrance in the Western Balkans) that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 898966.

Genocide Memorialization through Law in Bosnia and Herzegovina: Reconciling the Irreconcilable?

Carna Pistan

*Institute for Comparative Federalism, Eurac Research
Bolzano-Bozen, Italy*

Introduction

Almost thirty years since the end of the 1992–1995 war, Bosnia and Herzegovina continues to struggle with numerous difficult problems in terms of memorializing the past. In the war of the 1990s, the country was the scene of Europe’s single worst atrocity since the end of World War II—the massacre of more than 8,000 Bosnian Muslim (Bosniaks) men and boys by the Bosnian Serb Army.¹ This massacre has been adjudicated as a crime of genocide.² It occurred in and around the UN safe area of Srebrenica—a small town situated in northeastern Bosnia—in July 1995. During the war, Bosnia and Herzegovina was also a place in which other violations of human rights took place on a massive scale, including mass killings, ethnic cleansing, forced detention, torture, and rape.³ As an identity-driven conflict, the Bosnian war was particularly brutal, cruel, and emotionally charged.⁴ It resulted in around two-thirds of the population displaced, and approximately 100,000 casualties.⁵

Following the conflict, some progress has been achieved in establishing accountability and bringing war criminals to trial. Determining the legal truth about what had happened in the war and punishing the perpetrators—especially through the work of the International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia (ICTY)—has been deemed crucial for facilitating post-conflict reconciliation, providing justice to the victims, and preventing historical revisionism.⁶ Despite this, nationalist rhetoric denying war crimes, including the crime of genocide, and celebrating convicted war criminals has continuously persisted in the public sphere over the past decades. Revisionism and denial of well-documented and established wartime events have been promoted by state institutions, high-level politicians, and official representatives; a trend that has escalated in the past few years. All of this constitutes disrespect for the rule of law and the judicial system,

¹ According to the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial Center and Cemetery for the victims of the 1995 genocide, more than 8,372 men and boys were killed. See “Genocide in Srebrenica,” *Memorial Center Srebrenica*, accessed January 19, 2023, <https://srebrenicamemorial.org/en/page/genocide-in-srebrenica/26>.

² *Prosecutor v. Krstić*, International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia, Trial Chamber Judgement, August 2, 2001, IT-98-33-T, accessed January 20, 2023, <https://www.icty.org/en/case/krstic>.

³ Helsinki Watch, *War Crimes in Bosnia-Herzegovina: Vol. II* (USA: Human Rights Watch, 1992), 45, accessed January 22, 2023, <https://www.hrw.org/reports/pdfs/y/yugoslav/yugo.928/yugo928full.pdf>.

⁴ Nicholas Haysom, “Constitution Making and Nation Building,” in *Federalism in a Changing World: Learning from Each Other*, ed. Raoul Blindenbacher and Arnold Koller (London: McGill-Queen’s University Press, 2003), 216.

⁵ In late 1992, the Bosnian government sources indicated that about 200,000 people were killed in the war, while the UN Prosecutor’s office at the ICTY had put the number of dead at about 110,000. A more recent project entitled “The Bosnian Book of Dead,” led by Mirsad Tokača at the Research and Documentation Center in Sarajevo, finally revealed that at least 97,207 people were killed in the war and that this number could rise by a maximum of another 10,000 due to ongoing research. According to this study, 65% of those killed were Bosnian Muslims, 25% were Serbs, and more than 8% were Croats. See “Bosnia War Dead Figure Announced,” *BBC News*, June 21, 2007, accessed January 24, 2023, <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/europe/6228152.stm>.

⁶ See, for example, Claude Jorda, “The ICTY and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission in Bosnia and Herzegovina” (speech, Sarajevo, May 12, 2001), United Nations, International Criminal Tribunal for the former Yugoslavia, accessed January 20, 2023, <https://www.icty.org/en/press/icty-and-truth-and-reconciliation-commission-bosnia-and-herzegovina>.

two pillars of every democratic society.⁷ It further contradicts the most fundamental European values⁸ and represents a serious obstacle to lasting peace, stability, and reconciliation in the country.⁹

The 1995 Dayton Peace Agreement has so far failed to reverse such post-conflict developments. It split the country into two entities: the decentralized Bosniak-Croat Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina (itself composed of 10 cantons), and the centralized Serb-majority *Republika Srpska*. Although this solution ended the war, it has also maintained divisions along ethnic lines and high levels of mistrust between communities.¹⁰ The country's Constitution (adopted as Annex 4 of the Dayton Peace Accords) further precludes the achievement of reconciliation. As Andrew Schaap observes, for reconciliation to be possible, it requires taking the present as a point of a new beginning and memorializing this new beginning with the promise of *never again*. It further requires the invocation of a *we* as the basis of a new political order,¹¹ and this *we* should be as inclusive as possible.¹² There is no such *we* nor the promise of *never again* in the Bosnian Constitution. It invokes the three main ethnic groups—Bosniaks, Croats, and Serbs—labeling them “constituent peoples” and refers to ethnic minorities, as well as persons who do not declare affiliation with any particular group as “others.”¹³ The Constitution, consequently, reiterates ethnic divisions rather than favoring reconciliation, and divided societies produce divided memories along ethnic fault lines.¹⁴ In Bosnia and Herzegovina, three conflicting “constituent memories” about the war of the 1990s exist.¹⁵ They are ethnocentric, mutually exclusive, and irreconcilable.¹⁶ Each of them sees its ethnic group as a victim of historical injustices and perceives the conflict of the 1990s as a defensive liberation war.

⁷ See Lejla Gačanica and Caroline Finkeldey, *Calling War Atrocities by their Right Name. Regulating a Ban on Denial, Trivialisation, Justification or Condonation of Genocide, the Holocaust, Crimes Against Humanity or War Crimes* (Sarajevo: Forum Ziviler Friedensdienst—TRIAL International, 2019), 6, accessed January 19, 2023, <https://trialinternational.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Calling-War-Atrocities-by-their-Right-Name-TRIAL-ZFD-EN-2019.pdf>.

⁸ See, for example, European Commission, *Commission Staff Working Document: Bosnia and Herzegovina 2020 Report* (Brussels: European Commission, October 6, 2020), 27, accessed February 6, 2023, https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/bosnia_and_herzegovina_report_2020.pdf.

⁹ “High Representative Valentin Inzko Introduced Today Amendments to the BH Criminal Code: Forgiveness and Reconciliation are Most Important,” *Office of the High Representative* (OHR), (press release, Sarajevo, July 23, 2021), accessed February 3, 2023, www.ohr.int/high-representative-valentin-inzko-introduced-today-amendment-to-the-bh-criminal-code/.

¹⁰ See, for example, Roland Kostić, *Reconciling the Past and the Present: Evaluating the Dayton Peace Agreement 1995* (Uppsala: Uppsala University Press, 2009), 27.

¹¹ See Andrew Schaap, “The Time of Reconciliation and the Space for Politics,” in *Law and the Politics of Reconciliation*, ed. Scott Veitch (London: Routledge, 2007), 9.

¹² See Johannes Snyman, “Interpretation and the Politics of Memory,” *Acta Juridica*, no. 8 (1998), 312.

¹³ The Constitution offers a range of guarantees based on the prevalence of the rights of the three constituent peoples over citizenship rights. It denies, for example, to the citizens it labels as “others” the right to run for the Presidency and the House of Peoples (the upper house of Parliament). The European Court of Human Rights ruled that such constitutional provisions directly discriminate against ethnic minorities and persons who call themselves citizens of Bosnia and Herzegovina as they do not allow their equal participation in elections. See *Sejdić and Finci v. Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Grand Chamber Judgment, December 22, 2009; *Zornić v. Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Fourth Section Judgment, July 15, 2014, and *Šlaku v. Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Fifth Section Judgment, May 26, 2016. In deciding other cases concerning violations of the right to free elections, the same Court found that Bosnia's Constitution discriminates on the grounds of ethnic origin and place of residence. See *Pilav v. Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Fifth Section Judgment, June 9, 2016, and *Pudarić v. Bosnia and Herzegovina*, Fourth Section Judgment, December 8, 2020. Up to now, all attempts aimed at amending the Constitution to comply with these rulings have failed.

¹⁴ Diane F. Orentlicher, *That Someone Guilty Be Punished: The Impact of the ICTY in Bosnia* (New York: Open Society Justice Initiative, 2010), 48.

¹⁵ See Anida Sokol, “War Monuments: Instruments of Nation-Building in Bosnia and Herzegovina,” *Croatian Political Science Review* 51, no. 5 (2014), 105.

¹⁶ See, for example, Jelena Subotic, “Remembrance, Public Narratives, and Obstacles to Justice in the Western Balkans,” *Studies in Social Justice* 7, no. 2 (2013), 265.

An important attempt aimed at facilitating reconciliation and fighting against the growing culture of denial regarding the mass atrocities committed in the Bosnian War dates back to July 2021 when the then-outgoing High Representative Valentin Inzko imposed an amendment to the country's Criminal Code, which banned the denial of genocide and other war crimes and the glorification of war criminals. The Office of the High Representative is an *ad hoc* international institution created to support the implementation of the civilian aspects of the Dayton Peace Agreement. The amendment to the Criminal Code has been imposed by using the so-called Bonn Powers, which allow the High Representative to adopt binding decisions and remove public officials. Considering that this special set of powers has not been used in the past decade so as to not interfere with Bosnia's sovereignty, the imposed changes to the Criminal Code appeared even more relevant.¹⁷ According to the official press release accompanying the imposition of the legislation, the aim was to address a national legal framework that did not offer an adequate response to the issue of hate speech through the denial of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes.¹⁸

This article focuses on the memorialization of the 1992–1995 Bosnian War and its darkest chapter, the crime of genocide through the lens of the imposed genocide denial ban. It first positions the law penalizing the denial of genocide and other international crimes within the broader category of memory laws and then explores, through a comparative approach, its content and scope, as well as the reactions and consequences it has provoked up to now, especially in *Republika Srpska* where Srebrenica is located. The article argues that an externally imposed memory law cannot facilitate reconciliation in a post-conflict and deeply divided society. On the contrary, it shows that the genocide denial ban has triggered an internal memory war that has plunged the country into its most serious political and constitutional crisis since the war ended in 1995 and which required an intervention of the state-level Constitutional Court. While existing studies have criticized the 2021 law banning genocide denial, citing poor drafting, which does not allow prosecutions on its basis, and failure to facilitate inclusive societal discussions on past atrocities,¹⁹ this article maintains that the imposed legislation represents an important and necessary instrument. It preserves the judicially established truth about the Bosnian War and the legacy of the ICTY and provides, by mirroring Western European memory laws, a comprehensive legal framework capable of combatting an alarming normalization of genocide denial and the glorification of war criminals within society. In so doing, the imposed law positions in the center the victims of violence, thus aligning memorialization with a culture of democracy and respect for human rights. By examining Bosnia's law criminalizing genocide denial, the article further aims to contribute to genocide studies by illustrating how the law may respond to acts of denial of mass atrocities, as well as to the ongoing debate in legal studies on the legitimacy of memory laws in liberal democracies by introducing a perspective of a post-conflict society.

¹⁷ See Hamza Karčić, "Analysis: What Bosnia's New Genocide Denial Ban Means," *Anadolu Agency*, July 27, 2021, accessed February 7, 2023, <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/analysis/analysis-what-bosnias-new-genocide-denial-ban-means/2315421>. The decision banning genocide denial has opened a new phase of imposing legislation in the country. Among the most important decisions imposed by Inzko's successor, High Representative Christian Schmidt, see the "Decision Enacting the Law on Amendments to the Election Law of Bosnia and Herzegovina: 07/22," OHR, October 2, 2022, accessed January 28, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-the-law-on-amendments-to-the-election-law-of-bosnia-and-herzegovina-8/> and the "Decision Enacting Amendments to the Constitution of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina," OHR, October 2, 2022, accessed January 28, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-amendments-to-the-constitution-of-the-federation-of-bosnia-and-herzegovina-3/>.

¹⁸ Office of the High Representative, *High Representative Valentin Inzko*. First mentioned in note 9.

¹⁹ See Jessie Barton Hronešová and Jasmin Hasić, "The 2021 Memory Law in Bosnia and Herzegovina—Reconciliation or Polarization?," *Journal of Genocide Research* (2023), 1.

Memory Laws and the Criminalization of the Past

Laws banning the denial of genocide and other war crimes pertain to the vast category of memory laws. Both the Council of Europe and the literature define this type of legislation as legal provisions that “enshrine state-approved interpretations of crucial historical events and promote certain narratives about the past.”²⁰ While this definition mainly refers to national legislation, Sébastien Ledoux observes that the term memory laws more broadly includes resolutions and declarations on the interpretation of historical events passed by international and supranational institutions.²¹

Nikolay Koposov further distinguishes between non-punitive and punitive memory laws.²² The first sub-type includes declaratory laws that establish an official assessment of historical events but typically do not have a normative character. It further includes laws concerning very different subjects, ranging from acts on state symbols, remembrance days, and commemorations to laws on the creation of museums, construction of public monuments, introduction of historical events in school education, and more. This latter group of laws entails various rights and obligations for the State and citizens. Punitive memory laws, on the contrary, criminalize certain narratives about the past, such as the denial of the Holocaust and/or genocide, war crimes, and crimes against humanity. For Koposov, the core of the category of memory laws consists of punitive memory laws, while non-punitive memory laws have a peripheral character.²³

Nowadays, punitive memory laws exist in most European countries.²⁴ They first emerged in states such as Austria and Germany in the 1980s and then proliferated in other Western European democracies in the 1990s. As of the 2000s and 2010s, punitive memory laws also emerged in Central and Eastern Europe. The French Gayssot Act of 1990²⁵ set the standard for the adoption of similar legislation in European states and has been used as a model for international agreements.²⁶ It criminalized the denial of the Holocaust, war crimes, and crimes against humanity by expressly referring to the crimes defined in Article 6 of the Charter of the International Military Tribunal (IMT) as annexed in Article 2 of the London Agreement of 8 August 1945 (the Nuremberg Tribunal). While the aim of memory laws adopted in the 1980s was to prevent Holocaust negationism, the Gayssot Act expanded the scope to include war crimes and crimes against humanity as defined by international law. In addition, with the expansion of punitive memory laws in Western Europe in the 1990s, the notion of denial has

²⁰ See Council of Europe, “Memory Laws” and Freedom of Expression (Strasbourg: Council of Europe, July 2018), 1, accessed January 20, 2023, <https://rm.coe.int/factsheet-on-memory-laws-july2018-docx/16808c1690>, and Uladzislau Belavusau and Aleksandra Gliszczyńska-Grabias, “Introduction: Mapping a New Subject in Comparative Law and Transitional Justice,” in *Law and Memory: Towards Legal Governance of History*, ed. Uladzislau Belavusau and Aleksandra Gliszczyńska-Grabias (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017), 12.

²¹ Sébastien Ledoux, “Memory Laws in Europe: What Common Horizons are we Journeying Towards?,” *Magazine of the European Observatory on Memories*, March 11, 2022, accessed January 20, 2023, <https://europeanmemories.net/magazine/memory-laws-in-europe-what-common-horizons-are-we-journeing-towards/>.

²² Nikolay Koposov, *Memory Laws, Memory Wars: The Politics of the Past in Europe and Russia* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018), 6.

²³ *Ibid.*; see also Emanuela Fronza, *Memory and Punishment: Historical Denialism, Free Speech and the Limits of Criminal Law* (The Hague: T.M.C. Asser Press, 2018), 27, who distinguishes between two models of legal protection of memory: a soft model (remembrance laws) and a hard model (criminal statutes). The distinction between punitive and non-punitive memory laws has been further expanded by adding the category of quasi-memory laws, which includes citizenship laws that permit naturalization based on historical belonging. See Uladzislau Belavusau et al., “Memory Laws and Memory Wars in Poland, Russia and Ukraine,” *Jahrbuch des öffentlichen Rechts* 69, no. 1 (2021), 101.

²⁴ See Ledoux, *Memory Laws in Europe*, who notes that this type of legislation is specific to the civil law legal tradition, while common law countries are not familiar with it or only on a very small scale.

²⁵ *Loi No. 90-615 du 13 juillet 1990 tendant à réprimer tout acte raciste, antisémite ou xénophobe* (Law No. 90-615 of 13 July 1990 tending to repress any racist, anti-Semitic or xenophobic acts) of 1990 (Law No. 90-615, July 13, 1990), (Rep. of France), accessed February 10, 2023, <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000000532990>.

²⁶ Koposov, *Memory Laws, Memory Wars*, 82.

been replaced by a broader formula, as many of these laws also preclude the trivialization and justification of those crimes.²⁷

Over time, a lot has been written in favor and against this type of legislation. Proponents of punitive memory laws often base their arguments on the concept of “militant democracy” and view them as a preventative measure that criminal law uses against racism, anti-Semitism, and xenophobia, by prosecuting the incitement of violence or racial hatred. The purpose of their adoption is to condemn historical crimes and restore the dignity of the victims.²⁸ On the contrary, punitive memory laws have been often criticized for imposing an official interpretation of history, thus limiting the freedom of expression and historical research.²⁹ In the European legal tradition, however, freedom of expression is not an absolute right. While in the United States deniers are largely protected by the First Amendment’s free speech clause, the European Court of Human Rights (ECtHR) has consistently excluded Holocaust denial from the protection of Article 10 (freedom of expression) of the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), pointing to its anti-Semitic nature and qualifying it as an abuse of rights. For example, in *Garaudy v. France*, the ECtHR held that disputing the existence of clearly established historical events, such as the Holocaust, does not constitute scientific nor historical research, but is rather an effort to rehabilitate the National Socialist regime and accuse Holocaust victims of falsifying history. It further stated that denying crimes against humanity is one of the most serious forms of racial defamation of Jews and of incitement to hatred of them. It undermines the values on which the fight against racism and anti-Semitism is based and constitutes a serious threat to public order. Since such acts are incompatible with the fundamental values that the ECHR promotes, the ECtHR applied Article 17 (prohibition of abuse of rights) to the case and held that Holocaust denial is not protected by Article 10. In other words, it ruled that the protections in Article 17 could restrict the right to freedom of expression granted under Article 10 of the ECHR.³⁰

The same approach has not been followed in *Perinçek v. Switzerland*, concerning the criminal conviction of an applicant after publicly stating that “the allegations of the ‘Armenian genocide’ are an international lie.” The ECtHR found that the Swiss authorities violated Article 10 of the ECHR when convicting the applicant as he was discussing a matter of public interest and, therefore, his statements did not constitute a call for hatred or intolerance. It further considered that the context in which the applicant made the statements was not marked by heightened tensions and that these could not be regarded as affecting the dignity of Armenians to the point of enforcing criminal law.³¹ Similarly, in *Lehideux and Isorni v. France*, the ECtHR held that the conviction of the applicants, for publishing an article that described Marshal Philippe Pétain, head of state of Vichy France, in a favorable light, violated Article 10 of the

²⁷ See Aleksandra Gliszczynska-Grabias, “Penalizing Holocaust Denial: A View from Europe,” in *Global Antisemitism: A Crisis of Modernity*, ed. Charles Asher Small (Leiden: Brill Nijhoff Publishers, 2013), 240, who notes that to make the penal method effective, the legal definition of denial must be sufficiently broad to encompass concepts such as trivialization and justification. However, this extensive definition of denial also raises some doubts concerning the legal interpretation of such legally imprecise terms.

²⁸ See Belavusau and Gliszczynska-Grabias, *Introduction*, 10, noting that punitive memory laws have been central to the concept of militant democracy, which excludes the incitement to hatred from constitutionally protected rights of free expression to preserve liberal democracy. See also Grażyna Baranowska and Anna Wójcik, “In Defence of Europe’s memory laws,” *Eurozine*, November 6, 2017, accessed February 25, 2023, <https://www.eurozine.com/about-eurozine/>.

²⁹ See Josie Appleton et al., “Freedom for History? The Case Against Memory Laws,” *Free Speech Debate*, April 3, 2013, accessed February 26, 2023, <http://freespeechdebate.com/discuss/freedom-for-history-the-case-against-memory-laws/>; see also Paul Behrens, “Genocide Denial and the Law: A Critical Appraisal,” *Buffalo Human Rights Law Review* 21, no. 1 (2015), 27; Roger W. Smith, “Legislating Against Genocide Denial: Criminalizing Denial or Preventing Free Speech?,” *University of St. Thomas Journal of Law and Public Policy* 4, no. 2 (2010), 128.

³⁰ *Garaudy v. France*, Fourth Section Inadmissibility Decision, June 24, 2003. See also Paolo Lobba, “Holocaust Denial before the European Court of Human Rights: Evolution of an Exceptional Regime,” *European Journal of International Law* 26, no. 1 (2015), 237.

³¹ *Perinçek v. Switzerland*, Grand Chamber Judgment, October 15, 2015.

ECHR. It argued, in particular, that the case “does not belong to the category of clearly established historical facts—such as the Holocaust—whose negation or revision would be removed from the protection of Article 10 by Article 17.”³² Indications of what constitutes the category of “clearly established historical facts” may be extrapolated from Article 6 of the Additional Protocol on Cybercrime of 2003, which refers to acts constituting genocide or crimes against humanity, as defined by international law and recognized as such by final and binding decisions of the Nuremberg Tribunal, or of any other international Court established by relevant international instruments.³³

From Conflict Resolution to Nationalism

The expansion of punitive memory laws in Europe after 1990 denoted the emergence of a new model of conflict resolution and dealing with political violence. Although in the immediate post-World War II context the Genocide Convention of 1948 and the Geneva Conventions of 1949 introduced a legal foundation towards greater accountability for grave human rights crimes,³⁴ the political model advanced by nation-states from the end of the 1940s to the mid-1980s was the policy of forgetting, and amnesty as its legal corollary. This model resulted in the public absence (or also prohibition) of the memorialization of crimes and victims because this was considered a threat to peace, public order, and the continuation of the community.³⁵ In Spain, for example, after the demise of the Franco regime, amnesia was the outcome of a negotiated compromise between the successor elites.³⁶ By contrast, the proliferation of punitive memory laws in Western Europe occurred within the global growth of the human rights culture in the mid-1980s, when the emphasis was placed on the duty to prosecute crimes against humanity, genocide, and war crimes. This was followed by the establishment of *ad hoc* international criminal tribunals in Yugoslavia and Rwanda, the International Criminal Court, and some alternative and/or complementary mechanisms to criminal justice such as truth commissions.³⁷ Within this context, the emergence of punitive memory laws in the 1990s has guaranteed the public disclosure of crimes committed and punishment for their denial. It further gave rise to the recognition of, and reparations for, the victims of political violence.³⁸

The rise of European punitive memory laws cannot be properly understood without considering the attempts of the European Union (EU) to create a transnational European memory.³⁹ As of the 1990s, European institutions have promoted a model of remembrance centered on the memory of World War II and the Holocaust. Tony Judt argues, for example, that the inclusion of the Holocaust as an important element of national history was also one of the entrance tickets to the EU in the 2000s.⁴⁰ The EU Council Framework Decision on combating certain forms and expressions of racism and xenophobia by means of criminal law of 2008, further obliged EU member states to take the necessary measures to ensure the criminalization

³² *Lehideux and Isorni v. France*, Grand Chamber Judgment, September 23, 1998.

³³ Council of Europe, *Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime, Concerning the Criminalisation of Acts of a Racist and Xenophobic Nature Committed through Computer Systems* (European Treaty Series—No. 189), January 28, 2003, accessed February 25, 2023, <https://rm.coe.int/168008160f>.

³⁴ Luc Huyse, “Introduction: Tradition-Based Approaches in Peacemaking, Transitional Justice and Reconciliation Policies,” in *Traditional Justice and Reconciliation After Violent Conflict: Learning from African Experiences*, ed. Luc Huyse and Mark Salter (Stockholm: International IDEA, 2008), 2.

³⁵ Ledoux, *Memory Laws in Europe*.

³⁶ See, for example, Luc Huyse, “Justice After Transition: On the Choices Successor Elites Make in Dealing with the Past,” *Law & Social Inquiry* 20, no. 1 (1995), 51.

³⁷ Huyse, *Introduction*, 2.

³⁸ Ledoux, *Memory Laws in Europe*.

³⁹ See, for example, Aleida Assman, “Europe: A Community of Memory?,” *German Historical Institute Bulletin*, no. 40, 2017, 11; and Aline Sierp, “Integrating Europe, Integrating Memories: The EU’s Politics of Memory Since 1945,” in *The Transcultural Turn Interrogating Memory Between and Beyond Borders*, ed. Lucy Bond and Jessica Rapson (Berlin: De Gruyter, 2014), 106.

⁴⁰ Tony Judt, *Postwar: A History of Europe Since 1945* (New York: The Penguin Press, 2005), 803.

of public incitement to violence or hatred, including the dissemination or distribution of tracts, pictures, or other materials with racist or xenophobic content, as well as public condonation, denial, and gross trivialization of crimes of genocide, crimes against humanity, and war crimes as defined in Articles 6, 7, and 8 of the Statute of the International Criminal Court, and crimes defined in Article 6 of the IMT Charter, when directed against a group of persons or a member of such a group defined by reference to race, color, religion, descent or national or ethnic origin, and when the conduct is carried out in a manner likely to incite violence or hatred against such a group or a member of such a group.⁴¹

Despite this attempt to homogenize EU member states' legislation, punitive memory laws that proliferated in the 2000s and 2010s in countries of Central and Eastern Europe that have experienced illiberal or authoritarian turns, remain controversial. It has been noted, for example, that in liberal democracies, punitive memory laws are subject to more restrictive conditions than in illiberal states. For instance, Section 130(3) of the German Criminal Code (as reformed in 1994) establishes that statements denying or trivializing Nazi crimes must be made in a manner capable of disturbing public peace. Such additional criteria, which are needed to activate criminal sanctions, could potentially reduce tensions between punitive memory laws and freedom of speech and academic research.⁴² On the contrary, illiberal regimes rely on a much broader concept of criminal denial which triggers excessive and disproportional punishment by courts.⁴³ Nikolay Kaposov further observes that memory laws that emerged in Western Europe in the 1980s and 1990s contributed to the formation of a "cosmopolitan memory" centered around the Holocaust and crimes against humanity, and informed by the notion of state repentance. As such, they were an expression of a democratic culture of remembrance and their adoption was aimed to promote truth, peace, and reconciliation. By contrast, more recent memory laws adopted in some Central and Eastern European countries, are often employed as a tool for promoting nationalist versions of history and self-victimization of the community by shifting the blame for historical injustices entirely to others, notably Nazi Germany or Soviet Communism.⁴⁴ George Soroka and Félix Krawatzek similarly note that the first generation of memory laws sought to demythologize national histories and protect the memory of the victims. Their purpose was to integrate diverse societies, overcome previous cycles of violence, promote reconciliation, encourage international dialogue, and provide a safeguard for minority rights. On the contrary, the new generation of memory laws is typically focused on protecting the memory of the state or nation.⁴⁵ For instance, the Polish Holocaust law of 2018 criminalized references to the complicity of the Polish State and Polish nation in the crimes of the Holocaust, even if historians have long argued that while the Polish government did not have any role in the Holocaust, some individual Poles were complicit in the Nazi

⁴¹ European Union, Council Framework Decision 2008/913/JHA of 28 November 2008 on Combating Certain Forms and Expressions of Racism and Xenophobia by Means of Criminal Law, November 28, 2008 (2008/913/JHA), accessed February 25, 2023, https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_framw/2008/913/oj.

⁴² See Klaus Bachmann et al., "The Puzzle of Punitive Memory Laws: New Insights into the Origins and Scope of Punitive Memory Laws," *East European Politics and Societies and Cultures* 35, no. 4 (2021), 996; Laurent Pech, "The Law of Holocaust Denial in Europe: Towards a (Qualified) EU-Wide Criminal Prohibition," *Jean Monnet Working Paper 10/09* (New York: NYU School of Law, 2009), 10, observes, however, that German courts operate on the presumption that any utterance denying or downplaying Nazi crimes invariably poses, in itself, a threat to public peace, meaning that the mere existence of a potential and abstract threat is sufficient.

⁴³ Bachmann et al., *The Puzzle of Punitive Memory Laws*, 1003.

⁴⁴ Nikolay Kaposov, "Populism and Memory: Legislation of the Past in Poland, Ukraine, and Russia," *East European Politics and Societies and Cultures* 36, no. 1 (2022), 272.

⁴⁵ George Soroka and Félix Krawatzek, "Nationalism, Democracy, and Memory Laws," *Journal of Democracy* 30, no. 2 (2019), 157.

crimes.⁴⁶ In Russia, the law against the rehabilitation of Nazism of 2014 criminalized the dissemination of knowingly false information on the activities of the Soviet Union during World War II. Any public attempt to equate the aims and actions of the Soviet Union and Nazi Germany during the war, as well as to deny the decisive role of the Soviet people in the victory over fascism, has been banned. This includes, for example, arguments suggesting Soviet complicity in the invasion of Poland for signing the Molotov Ribbentrop Pact of 1939.⁴⁷ In Ukraine, the decommunization law of 2015 defined Nazi collaborationist forces involved in mass murders during World War II, including the Ukrainian Insurgent Army and the Organization of Ukrainian Nationalists, as “fighters for Ukraine’s independence.” In Turkey, the original version of Article 301 of the Criminal Code prohibited the “denigration of Turkishness” and was used in the past by the state for prosecuting those questioning Turkey’s denial of the Armenian genocide.⁴⁸ All of these are examples of what Andrea Pető calls illiberal memory politics,⁴⁹ which aims to protect the memory of oppressive regimes rather than the memory of their victims. It has been further argued that in Central and Eastern Europe, memory laws have been transformed into a preferred instrument of memory wars within and between states.⁵⁰

Bosnia’s Genocide Denial Law: Contents and Scope

The High Representative’s decision banning the denial of genocide and other war crimes in Bosnia and Herzegovina⁵¹ can be ascribed to the category of punitive memory laws criminalizing certain statements about the past. However, it also differs from the general definition of memory laws in that it has been internationally imposed and does not thus reflect state-sponsored memories. It was precisely the failure of a decade-long series of attempts to pass a punitive memory law by the Bosnian Parliament that led the Office of the High Representative to impose the amendment to the Criminal Code from the above.⁵² The imposed law further reflects the original intent of memory laws. It has been adopted as an instrument aimed at protecting the memory of the victims and promoting truth, reconciliation, and a peaceful and prosperous future for the country.⁵³ In its content, it follows the standards originally set by the French Gassyout Act and the EU Framework Decision, but it has also expanded its scope to include the atrocities committed in the Bosnian War.

More specifically, the amendment changed Article 145a of the Bosnian Criminal Code by introducing penalties that range from three months to three years imprisonment for the public incitement to violence or hatred against a person or group on the basis of their race, color, religion, descent or national or ethnic origin (para. 2). The central aspect of the law is

⁴⁶ See, for example, Peter Vermeersch, “Victimhood as Victory: The Role Of Memory Politics in the Process of de-Europeanization in East Central Europe,” *Global Discourse: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Current Affairs* 9, no. 1 (2019), 113, who notes that the 2018 Holocaust law was an expression of a state-sponsored approach that argued that only victimhood captures the essence of Polish national history and that such national victimhood excludes the possibility of perpetrators and guilt.

⁴⁷ See, for example, Carna Pistan, “Alarming Alterations: How Memory Politics Turned the Russian Constitution into a War Weapon,” PONARS Eurasia Policy Memo No. 798, George Washington University, September 26, 2022, accessed February 26, 2023, <https://www.ponarseurasia.org/alarming-alterations-how-memory-politics-turned-the-russian-constitution-into-a-war-weapon/>.

⁴⁸ Jahnisa Tate, “Turkey’s Article 301: A Legitimate Tool for Maintaining Order or a Threat to Freedom of Expression,” *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law* 37, no. 1 (2008), 181.

⁴⁹ Andrea Pető, “The Illiberal Memory Politics in Hungary,” *Journal of Genocide Research* 24, no. 2 (2022), 241.

⁵⁰ Koposov, *Memory Laws, Memory Wars*, 11; Soroka and Krawatzek, *Nationalism, Democracy*, 158.

⁵¹ “HR’s Decision on Enacting the Law on Amendment to the Criminal Code of Bosnia and Herzegovina,” OHR, July 23, 2021, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/hrs-decision-on-enacting-the-law-on-amendment-to-the-criminal-code-of-bosnia-and-herzegovina>.

⁵² Nejra Dzaferagic, “Bosnia Under Pressure to Adopt Srebrenica Genocide Denial Law,” *Balkan Insight*, April 16, 2021, accessed January 21, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2021/04/16/bosnia-under-pressure-to-adopt-srebrenica-genocide-denial-law/>.

⁵³ Office of the High Representative, *High Representative Valentin Inzko*.

given by the next paragraph (para. 3), which introduced prison sentences from six months to five years for anyone who publicly condones, denies, grossly trivializes, or tries to justify a crime of genocide, crimes against humanity, or a war crime when three conditions are met: a) those crimes are established by a final adjudication pursuant to the IMT Charter appended to the 1945 London Agreement, the ICTY, the International Criminal Court, or a court in Bosnia and Herzegovina; b) the offense is directed against a group of persons or a member of a group defined by race, color, religion, descent or national or ethnic origin, and; c) the offense should be done in a way that is likely to incite violence or hatred (para. 3).

The imposed law also introduced prison sentences of not less than one year for public dissemination or distribution of tracts, pictures, or other material related to those crimes (para. 4). If the criminal offense disturbs public peace and order, or is threatening, abusive or insulting (para. 5), or is committed by a public official (para. 7), the perpetrator is punished by not less than three years imprisonment. The same punishment is applicable for glorifying in any way persons sentenced by a final judgment for genocide, crimes against humanity, or a war crime, including by giving them recognition, award, memorial, any kind of memento, or any privilege or similar, or by naming a public object such as a street, square, park, bridge, an institution, building, municipality or a city or similar, or registering a brand, after or under their name.

What should be noted is that the amendment to the Bosnian Criminal Code did not introduce an overall ban on genocide denial but in line with Western European punitive memory laws and the EU Framework Decision, limited the persecution to judicially established crimes and to expressions motivated by violence or hatred based on ethnic or other discriminatory grounds. Alternative approaches and interpretations of wartime events remain possible for scientific reasons, for example, or in dissenting opinions of national judges. The imposed legislation thus offers a balance between protection from hate speech and protection of freedom of expression.

A Tool that Contributes to Reconciliation?

Another issue is whether an externally imposed memory law can promote reconciliation in a deeply divided society as stated by the Office of the High Representative.⁵⁴ Although extensively discussed in academic literature, reconciliation remains a complex and controversial term. It has sometimes been associated with the concept of forgiveness, and sometimes with terms such as “coexistence” or “social reconstruction,” thus implying that it does not necessarily need elements of forgiving.⁵⁵ Reconciliation has been further described as both a goal and a process, and in this latter sense it has been defined as a “complex set of processes that involve building or rebuilding relationships, often in the aftermath of massive and widespread human rights violations.”⁵⁶ It can occur between individuals, groups, and societies, or between the population and the state/institutions, while its goals are to prevent the conflict from re-escalating into violence and to create sustainable peace.⁵⁷ Reconciliation has often been associated with transitional justice mechanisms, such as truth commissions, or war crimes tribunals, as it is believed that combining some forms of both restorative justice and retributive justice facilitates its achievement.⁵⁸

Despite the lack of consensus on how to understand reconciliation, most authors would agree that it cannot be imposed from the outside. David Bloomfield observes, for example, that international actors may be present and support national initiatives, but reconciliation remains

⁵⁴ Ibid.

⁵⁵ See Martina Fisher, “Transitional Justice and Reconciliation: Theory and Practice,” in *Advanced Conflict Transformation: The Berghof Handbook II*, ed. Beatrix Austin et al. (Opladen: Barbara Budrich, 2011), 406.

⁵⁶ Paul Seils, “The Place of Reconciliation in Transitional Justice,” ICTJ briefing, June 2017, 1, accessed March 20, 2023, <https://www.ictj.org/publication/reconciliation-transitional-justice>; see also Luc Huyse, “The Process of Reconciliation,” in *Reconciliation After Violent Conflict. A Handbook*, ed. David Bloomfield et al. (Stockholm: International IDEA, 2005), 19.

⁵⁷ Seils, *The Place of Reconciliation*, 1.

⁵⁸ See, for example, Paul R. Williams and Michael P. Scharf, *Peace with Justice? War Crimes and Accountability in the Former Yugoslavia* (Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2002).

an internal affair.⁵⁹ Donna Pankhurst similarly argues that reconciliation is generally a more domestic affair in which the roles of members of the international community should be limited to supporting what emerges from within societies.⁶⁰ Such statements are, of course, particularly relevant in debates about the role of externally imposed international tribunals within reconciliation processes. In this sense, Antonio Cassese believed that by delivering justice, international tribunals can help reconciliation.⁶¹ The UN Resolution 1534 confirmed this vision by stating that the ICTY has contributed to lasting peace and security and national reconciliation.⁶² Other authors have noted, however, a more ambivalent role of international tribunals in reconciliation processes. For instance, Donna E. Arzt stresses that in Bosnia's *Republika Srpska*, the ICTY has been seen as a distant mechanism imposed from the outside.⁶³ James Meernik argues that the ICTY has exercised little effect on societal peace,⁶⁴ while John B. Allcock claims that the ICTY has fueled nationalist discourses about the war.⁶⁵ Laurel E. Fletcher and Harvey M. Weinstein further argue that the expectations that the ICTY's work could be expanded beyond its legal mandate and that it would contribute to reconciliation among former warring groups, have proved to be unrealistic and that such expectations might "undermine the important contributions that international trials can make to post-conflict societies."⁶⁶ Recent studies have similarly concluded that the ICTY's trials have not contributed to inter-ethnic reconciliation.⁶⁷

Similar assumptions can be transposed to externally imposed memory laws. In this sense, James Hughes and Denisa Kostovicova have underlined the contradictory logic between the external construction of norms and the efforts of their domestic imposition. Jasna Dragović-Soso has also noted the limited capacity of external actors to influence domestic processes of confronting a traumatic recent past.⁶⁸ When, for example, the Serbian Parliament adopted the 2010 declaration on Srebrenica as a formal apology for the 1995 genocide, it did not represent a turning point in Serbia's process of confronting the past because it was adopted to satisfy EU expectations within the country's integration process.⁶⁹ Despite the fact that the law banning genocide denial imposed in Bosnia and Herzegovina resembles the Western European legislation, which was adopted, among others, to facilitate reconciliation, it remains unlikely that an internationally imposed memory law can foster reconciliatory politics in a deeply divided post-conflict society.⁷⁰

⁵⁹ David Bloomfield, "Reconciliation: An Introduction," in *Reconciliation After Violent Conflict. A Handbook*, ed. David Bloomfield et al. (Stockholm: International IDEA, 2005), 10.

⁶⁰ Donna Pankhurst, "Issues of Justice and Reconciliation in Complex Political Emergencies: Conceptualising Reconciliation, Justice and Peace," *Third World Quarterly* 20, no. 1 (1999), 255.

⁶¹ Antonio Cassese, "Reflections on International Criminal Justice," *Modern Law Review* 61, no. 1 (1998), 6.

⁶² United Nations, *Security Council Resolution 1534*, March 26, 2004 (UN Doc. S/RES/1534).

⁶³ Donna E. Arzt, "Views on the Ground: The Local Perception of International Criminal Tribunals in the Former Yugoslavia and Sierra Leone," *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 603, no. 1 (2006), 226.

⁶⁴ James Meernik, "Justice and Peace? How the International Criminal Tribunal Affects Societal Peace in Bosnia," *Journal of Peace Research* 42, no. 3 (2005), 287.

⁶⁵ John B. Allcock, "The International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia," in *Confronting the Yugoslav Controversies: A Scholars' Initiative*, ed. Charles Ingrao and Thomas A. Emmert (West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2009), 367.

⁶⁶ Laurel E. Fletcher and Harvey M. Weinstein, "A World unto Itself? The Application of International Justice in the Former Yugoslavia," in *My Neighbor, My Enemy: Justice and Community in the Aftermath of Mass Atrocity*, ed. Eric Stover and Harvey M. Weinstein (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004), 30.

⁶⁷ Janine Clark, *International Trials and Reconciliation: Assessing the Impact of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia* (New York City: Routledge, 2015).

⁶⁸ Jasna Dragović-Soso, "Apologising for Srebrenica: The Declaration of the Serbian Parliament, the European Union and the Politics of Compromise," *East European Politics* 28, no. 2 (2012), 163.

⁶⁹ Ibid.

⁷⁰ In this sense, see Carna Pistan, "Call it by its Right Name: Criminalizing Genocide Denial in Bosnia and Herzegovina," *Verfassungsblog*, August 23, 2021, accessed February 7, 2023, <https://verfassungsblog.de/call-it-by-its-right-name/>; see also Hronešová and Hasić, *The 2021 Memory Law*, 17. First mentioned in note 19.

In other words, for its potential to promote reconciliation, the law banning the denial of genocide and other international crimes should have been adopted in Bosnia and Herzegovina by national institutions. That would have been a clear signal of former enemies coming together to create a shared understanding of the painful past and build a bridge toward a common future. This does not mean, however, that the imposed law does not represent an important and necessary instrument. Rather than reconciliation being a goal in itself, the imposed law should be seen as setting the foundations upon which reconciliation may be built in the future; the law protects the judicially established truth and the legacy of the ICTY and provides a legal framework capable of combatting genocide denial and the celebration of its perpetrators.

Protecting the Judicially Established Truth and the Legacy of the ICTY

Although the imposed amendment to Bosnia's Criminal Code does not exclude a much broader application, including, for example, the Holocaust denial ban, its primary aim is to preserve the judicially established facts and truth regarding the mass atrocities committed in the Bosnian war. While the role of the ICTY in reconciliation may be contentious, its significant contribution to reconstructing wartime events is undeniable.⁷¹ Since its establishment in May 1993, the Yugoslav Tribunal has produced through its investigations and proceedings, an extensive legal archive documenting crimes of war. As Iva Vukušić notes, this archive contains approximately 2400 linear meters of physical records and 1.5 petabytes of digital records, including both judicial and non-judicial records (articles, films, and reports documenting a war, clothing, death certificates, photographs of victims, testimonies of victims and accused, and courtroom session recordings).⁷² Following the ICTY's official closure in December 2017, its legal archive has assumed a memorial function. As Kirsten Campbell observes, it has become a source that produces legal memory,⁷³ or what Mark J. Osiel calls "international memory," to describe the impact of international criminal proceedings on the creation of collective memory.⁷⁴ Undoubtedly, one of the ICTY's most important results has been labeling the massacre in Srebrenica as genocide. In its landmark *Krstić* case, the ICTY Trial Chamber ruled that the mass killings of more than 7,000 Bosnian Muslim men and boys and the forced deportation of more than 25,000 women, children, and the elderly in July 1995, resulted in the physical disappearance of the Bosnian Muslim population from the town of Srebrenica, and qualifies as a crime of genocide.⁷⁵ Following this verdict, the ICTY and its successor, the International Residual Mechanism for Criminal Tribunals, found several other officials of *Republika Srpska* guilty of genocide, most notably its former President Radovan Karadžić, and General Ratko Mladić—both sentenced to life imprisonment.⁷⁶ In 2007, the International Court of Justice also ruled that the massacre committed in Srebrenica was an act of genocide.⁷⁷

⁷¹ See, for example, Ger Duijzings, "Commemorating Srebrenica: Histories of Violence and the Politics of Memory in Eastern Bosnia," in *The New Bosnian Mosaic: Identities, Memories and Moral Claims in a Post-War Society*, ed. Xavier Bougarel et al. (Burlington: Ashgate Publishing, 2007), 146.

⁷² Iva Vukušić, "Archives of Mass Violence: Understanding and Using ICTY Trial Records," *Comparative Southeast European Studies* 70, no. 4 (2022), 586.

⁷³ Kirsten Campbell, "The Laws of Memory: The ICTY, the Archive, and Transitional Justice," *Social & Legal Studies* 22, no. 2, (2012), 247; see also Kristen Perrin, "Memory at the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY): Discussions on Remembering and Forgetting within Victim Testimonies," *East European Politics and Societies and Cultures* 30, no. 2 (2016), 270.

⁷⁴ Mark J. Osiel, *Mass Atrocity, Collective Memory, and the Law* (New Brunswick: Transaction Publishers, 1997), 236.

⁷⁵ *Prosecutor v. Krstić*, Trial Chambers Judgment, para. 595; see also *Prosecutor v. Krstić*, Appeals Chamber Judgment, April 19, 2004, IT-98-33-A.

⁷⁶ See *Prosecutor v. Karadžić*, Trial Chambers Judgment, March 24, 2016, IT-95-5/18-T; *Prosecutor v. Mladić*, Trial Chambers Judgment, November 11, 2017, IT-09-92), and *Prosecutor v. Mladić*, Appeals Chamber Judgment, June 8, 2021, MICT-13-56-A.

⁷⁷ *Bosnia and Herzegovina v. Serbia and Montenegro*, GL No. 91, February 26, 2007. Also called the Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide.

While the ICTY played a crucial role in creating legal memories, the High Representative has become an important actor in preserving this judicially established truth. The 2021 genocide denial ban is not the first memory law imposed in the country. Over the years, the Office of the High Representative has imposed several non-punitive memory laws, including those related to state symbols (the flag,⁷⁸ the anthem,⁷⁹ and the coat-of-arms⁸⁰); the preservation of national monuments;⁸¹ the location of a cemetery and monument for the victims of Srebrenica;⁸² the establishment of the Foundation of the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery,⁸³ and the Center for the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery for the Victims of the 1995 Genocide.⁸⁴ As observed by Lara J. Nettelfield and Sarah E. Wagner, the latter law, while establishing the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial Center, specifically mentioned the verdict of the International Court of Justice, emphasizing that genocide was committed in Srebrenica.⁸⁵ It has been changed, more recently, by High Representative Christian Schmidt to facilitate the work of the Memorial Center.⁸⁶ The ICTY legacy has been additionally integrated into memory sites, most notably the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial Center, not only through its very existence, but also, for example, through displays hanging on walls with names, pictures, victim testimonies, and footage of proceedings, accusations, and sentences of the convicted war criminals.

Rather than resulting in a single accepted shared narrative of what occurred during the war,⁸⁷ the legal memories created by the ICTY and protected by the Office of the High

⁷⁸ “Decision Imposing the Law on the Flag of BiH,” OHR, February 4, 1998, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-imposing-the-law-on-the-flag-of-bih/>.

⁷⁹ “Decision Imposing the Law on the National Anthem of BiH,” OHR, June 25, 1999, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-imposing-the-law-on-the-national-anthem-of-bih/>.

⁸⁰ “Decision on the Shape and Design of the Coat-of-Arms of BiH,” OHR, May 18, 1998, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-on-the-shape-and-design-of-the-coat-of-arms-of-bih/>.

⁸¹ “Decision Amending the Federation Law on Preservation of Assets Declared National Monuments of BiH Under Decisions of the Commission for Protection of National Monuments,” OHR, August 2, 2002, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-amending-the-federation-law-on-preservation-of-assets-declared-national-monuments-of-bih-under-decisions-of-the-commission-for-protection-of-national-monuments/>; “Decision Imposing the RS Law on Implementation of Decisions of the Commission to Preserve National Monuments Established under Annex 8 of the Dayton Peace Agreement,” OHR, August 2, 2002, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-imposing-the-rs-law-on-implementation-of-decisions-of-the-commission-to-preserve-national-monuments-established-under-annex-8-of-the-dayton-peace-agreement/>.

⁸² “Decision on the Location of a Cemetery and a Monument for the Victims of Srebrenica,” OHR, October 25, 2000, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-on-the-location-of-a-cemetery-and-a-monument-for-the-victims-of-srebrenica/>.

⁸³ “Decision Establishing and Registering the Foundation of the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery,” OHR, May 10, 2001, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-establishing-and-registering-the-foundation-of-the-srebrenica-potocari-memorial-and-cemetery/>.

⁸⁴ “Decision Enacting the Law on the Center for the Srebrenica-Potocari Memorial and Cemetery for the Victims of the 1995 Genocide,” OHR, June 25, 2007, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-the-law-on-the-center-for-the-srebrenica-potocari-memorial-and-cemetery-for-the-victims-of-the-1995-genocide/>.

⁸⁵ Lara J. Nettelfield and Sarah E. Wagner, *Srebrenica in the Aftermath of Genocide* (Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014), 135.

⁸⁶ “Decision Enacting the Law on Amendments to the Law on the Center for the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery for the Victims of the 1995 Genocide,” OHR, February 21, 2023 accessed March 13, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-the-law-on-amendments-to-the-law-on-the-center-for-the-srebrenica-potocari-memorial-and-cemetery-for-the-victims-of-the-1995-genocide-2/>. The adjustment allows for unspent funds originally assigned for burials to be used for other purposes with the prior consent of the donors. See also Office of the High Representative, “High Representative Enables Better Functioning of Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial Center” (press release, Sarajevo, February 21, 2022), accessed March 13, 2023, www.ohr.int/high-representative-valentin-inzko-introduced-today-amendment-to-the-bh-criminal-code/.

⁸⁷ See, for example, Jennifer Trahan, “Examining the Benchmarks by which to Evaluate the ICTY’s Legacy,” in *Bosnian Genocide Denial and Triumphalism: Origins, Impact and Prevention*, ed. Sead Turčalo and Hikmet Karčić (Sarajevo: University of Sarajevo, 2021), 75.

Representative, represent a fourth (international) narrative of wartime events, which is competing in the country with the divisive “constituent memories” promoted by the three ethnic groups involved in the conflict. The ICTY decisions, however, certainly fall into the category of “clearly established historical facts” developed by the ECtHR, which includes acts constituting genocide or crimes against humanity, as defined by international law and recognized as such by any international Court. This means that the Srebrenica Genocide would enjoy before the ECtHR the same exceptional regime as the Holocaust, whose denial is removed from the protection of the ECHR.

Fighting Against the Culture of Denialism and Triumphalism

Despite the rulings of international Courts and overwhelming forensic evidence, politicians and institutions in *Republika Srpska* have been engaged in systematic genocide denial since the war ended in 1995. Hikmet Karčić notes that it has become even more institutionalized since the 2010s.⁸⁸ The three most common strategies of genocide denial include disputing the number and identities of the victims, the use of conspiracy theories that cast doubt on the rulings of international courts, and triumphalist national historical revisionism.⁸⁹ For example, Mladen Grujičić, the first Serb mayor of post-war Srebrenica elected in 2016 has repeatedly denied that the ICTY has ever proved that the Srebrenica massacre was a genocide.⁹⁰ Milorad Dodik, now President of *Republika Srpska* (and formerly the Serb member of Bosnia’s tripartite presidency), called the Srebrenica Genocide “a fabricated myth,” promoted conspiracy theories to contradict the judicially established facts on genocide, and even named a student dormitory after Karadžić, one of the convicted war criminals.⁹¹ In 2016, the Parliament of *Republika Srpska* awarded several convicted war criminals with honors.⁹² More recently, it also set up a truth commission, largely composed of foreign academics, to investigate the sufferings of all peoples in the Srebrenica region in the period from 1992 to 1995. On July 21, 2021, the commission issued a report that concluded that a genocide did not happen in Srebrenica, minimized the number of victims, and portrayed Bosniaks as the aggressor and the Bosnian Serbs as victims.⁹³ Menachem Z. Rosensaft called this report an “embarrassment to scholarship” and a “legal and factual abomination.”⁹⁴ Monuments, murals, and graffiti celebrating convicted war criminals as heroes, and streets and squares named after them, are decorating many cities in

⁸⁸ Hikmet Karčić, “Srebrenica Genocide Denial: From Dodik to TikTok,” in *Bosnian Genocide Denial Triumphalism: Origins, Impact and Prevention*, ed. Sead Turčalo and Hikmet Karčić (Sarajevo: University of Sarajevo, 2021), 61.

⁸⁹ See, for example, Monica Hanson Green, *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2020* (Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, May 2020), accessed February 16, 2023, <https://weremember.gov.tr/documents/Srebrenica-Genocide-Denial-Report-min.pdf>.

⁹⁰ See, for example, Igor Spaic, “Srebrenica’s Serb Mayor Repeats Denial of Genocide,” *Balkan Insight*, April 13, 2017, accessed February 15, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2017/04/13/srebrenica-s-serb-mayor-repeats-denial-of-genocide-04-13-2017/>.

⁹¹ See, for example, Zamira Rahim, “Srebrenica Massacre is ‘Fabricated Myth’, Bosnian Serb Leader Says.” *The Independent*, April 14, 2019, accessed February 16, 2023, <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/europe/srebrenica-massacre-genocide-milorad-dodik-bosnia-myth-a8869026.html>.

⁹² See, for example, Danijel Kovacevic, “Bosnian Serbs Reject Call to Revoke War Criminals’ Honours,” *Balkan Insight*, May 12, 2021, accessed February 16, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2021/05/12/bosnian-serbs-reject-call-to-revoke-war-criminals-honours/>.

⁹³ Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Sufferings of all People in the Srebrenica Region Between 1992 and 1995, *Concluding Report of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Suffering of All People in the Srebrenica Region Between 1992 and 1995*, July 21, 2021, accessed March 20, 2023, <https://incomfis-srebrenica.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Srebrenica%20Commission%20report%20-%20English%20lan.pdf>.

⁹⁴ Menachem Z. Rosensaft, “Deceptive Report Escalates Srebrenica Genocide Denial Campaign,” *Just Security*, July 29, 2021, accessed February 16, 2023, <https://www.justsecurity.org/77628/deceptive-report-escalates-srebrenica-genocide-denial-campaign/>.

*Republika Srpska*⁹⁵ and a 2018 poll revealed that 74 percent of Serbs in *Republika Srpska* consider Radovan Karadžić to be a war hero.⁹⁶

The persistent glorification of war criminals has resulted in the normalization of genocide denial within society, as well as the implicit affirmation that genocide is an *acceptable* act.⁹⁷ In the 10-stage model of genocide, developed by Gregory H. Stanton,⁹⁸ genocide denial is the final stage of genocide and among the surest indicators of its repetition. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, in addition to widespread genocide denial, the trend went even a step further culminating in the glorification of convicted war criminals. Hariz Halilovich calls this phase “triumphalism” and argues that it represents stage 11 of genocide.⁹⁹ Bosnia and Herzegovina might be a singular case of triumphalism, but it shows what can happen when a post-conflict society lacks an appropriate legal framework punishing genocide denial. A punitive memory law thus appears to be much needed in a disturbing context of normalization of genocide denial, triumphalism, and a growing culture of impunity. As has been rightly observed, revisionism in Bosnia and Herzegovina has nothing to do with allowing a plurality of approaches and interpretations of historical atrocities, but it is a rewriting of history “with little or no respect for facts.”¹⁰⁰

Triggering a Memory War

While the criminalization of genocide denial has been welcomed by the relatives of the victims and Bosniak politicians,¹⁰¹ in the absence of an internal political will to adjust past wrongs it has also triggered a memory war with *Republika Srpska*, whose institutions firmly rejected the imposed legislation. Milorad Dodik immediately announced that Serbs would not accept the imposed law, that genocide did not happen, and called the imposed law the “last nail in the coffin of Bosnia and Herzegovina.” He further threatened the country’s dissolution and encouraged the Parliament of *Republika Srpska* to decide on an “institutional response” to the imposed denial ban.¹⁰² The National Assembly of *Republika Srpska* responded by passing the law on the non-application of the High Representative’s decision. It established that the genocide denial ban would not apply in *Republika Srpska* and that the entity’s authorities would

⁹⁵ Nejra Dzaferovic, “Bosnian Streets and Squares Named After War Criminals,” *Balkan Insight*, May 19, 2020, accessed February 16, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2020/05/19/bosnian-streets-and-squares-named-after-war-criminals/>.

⁹⁶ “What are the 10 Stages of Genocide?,” *Al Jazeera*, July 10, 2020, accessed February 16, 2023, <https://www.aljazeera.com/amp/news/2020/7/10/what-are-the-10-stages-of-genocide>.

⁹⁷ Sabahudin Šarić, “The Denial of Genocide in Srebrenica in the Context of Strengthening Neo-fascism and Relativization of the Holocaust in Europe,” *Bosnian Studies* V, no. 1 (2021), 65.

⁹⁸ Gregory H. Stanton, “Ten Stages of Genocide,” *Genocide Watch*, accessed February 17, 2023, <https://www.genocidewatch.com/tenstages>.

⁹⁹ Hariz Halilovich, “25 Years After Srebrenica: ‘Local’ Genocide in a Global Context,” *Bosnian Genocide Denial and Triumphalism: Origins, Impact and Prevention*, ed. Sead Turčalo and Hikmet Karčić, (Sarajevo: University of Sarajevo, 2021), 115.

¹⁰⁰ Adem Mehmedović et al., *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2021* (Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, June 2021), accessed February 17, 2023, <https://srebrenicamemorial.org/assets/files/1625819683-srebrenica-genocide-denial-report-2021-english-language.pdf>.

¹⁰¹ Nermina Kuloglija and Azra Husaric Omerovic, “Bosnian Genocide Denial Ban Pleases Survivors, Angers Serbs,” *Balkan Insight*, July 23, 2021, accessed February 15, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2021/07/23/bosnian-genocide-denial-ban-pleases-survivors-angers-serbs/>.

¹⁰² “Sarajevo, Dodik names Inzko’s Decision on Genocide Denial the ‘Last Nail in BiH’s Coffin,’” *NI*, July 23, 2021, accessed February 15, 2023, <https://ba.n1info.com/english/news/dodik-names-inzkos-decision-on-genocide-denial-the-last-nail-in-bihs-coffin/>.

not cooperate with Bosnian authorities in applying the imposed decision.¹⁰³ This has practically legitimized genocide denial and the celebration of its perpetrators within the borders of *Republika Srpska*. At the same time, an amendment to the entity's Criminal Code has been approved, introducing prison terms of up to fifteen years for calling *Republika Srpska* a "genocidal creation," or for disrespecting its symbols, independence, and territory.¹⁰⁴ This has been followed by repeated calls from the entity's leadership to block the State-level institutions, and by pushing forward policies aimed at provoking a *de facto* secession; in particular, by trying to separate *Republika Srpska's* military, police, tax administration, and the judiciary from the central Bosnian government, all actions contrary to the Dayton Peace Agreement.¹⁰⁵

Both the law on the non-application of the genocide denial ban, and the amendment to *Republika Srpska's* Criminal Code resemble the illiberal memory laws currently thriving in Central and Eastern European countries experiencing authoritarian or illiberal shifts. They aim to protect the Serb majority from accusations of having committed international crimes, rather than honor the memory of the victims of war crimes and genocide. The two laws may be further considered as an expression of genocide triumphalism. As Hikmet Karčić observes, the term triumphalism not only covers the celebration of perpetrators but also of their legacy; that is, the "ethnically cleansed *Republika Srpska* entity."¹⁰⁶ Following their adoption, the Bosniak Caucus in the Council of Peoples—a body that oversees decisions made by the National Assembly of *Republika Srpska*—referred the two laws to the entity's Constitutional Court. In late September 2021, however, the Committee for the Protection of the Vital Interest of the Constitutional Court of *Republika Srpska* rejected both cases by claiming that the contested legislation did not violate the vital interest of the Bosniak people as it applies "equally to all citizens."¹⁰⁷ Seven delegates of the Council of Peoples then referred the law on non-application of the High Representative decision to the Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina.

The Intervention of the Constitutional Court

In reviewing the constitutionality of the law rejecting the application of the genocide denial ban in the *Republika Srpska*, the Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina first clarified the legal position of the High Representative in the Bosnian legal order, and the origins of his powers.¹⁰⁸ It specified, in particular, that the High Representative has been established by Annex 10 of the Dayton Peace Agreement as an agent of the international community, while his special set of powers, including the authority to enact laws when the Bosnian Parliament is unable, or unwilling to act, was introduced by the 1997 Bonn Declaration. The Constitutional Court further clarified that the political situation in Bosnia and Herzegovina is not unique as similar political circumstances were experienced by other states in the past, including the mandates under the regime of the League of Nations and, to some extent, Germany and Austria

¹⁰³ *Zakon o neprimjenjivanju Odluke Visokog predstavnika kojom se donosi Zakon o dopuni Krivičnog zakona Bosne i Hercegovine* (Law on Non-Applicability of the Decision the High Representative Enacting the Law on Amendment to the Criminal Code of Bosnia and Herzegovina) of 2021 (Law No. 02/1-021-584/21, July 30, 2021), (*Republika Srpska*), accessed February 16, 2023, <https://www.narodnaskupstinars.net/?q=la/akti/usvojeni-zakoni/zakon-o-neprimjenjivanju-odluke-visokog-predstavnika-kojom-se-donosi-zakon-o-dopuni-krivicnog-zakona-bosne-i-hercegovine>.

¹⁰⁴ *Zakon o dopuni Krivičnog zakonika Republike Srpske* (Law on Amendments to the Criminal Code of Republika Srpska) of 2021, (Law No. 02/1-021-586/21, July 30, 2021), (*Republika Srpska*), accessed February 16, 2023, <https://www.narodnaskupstinars.net/?q=la/akti/usvojeni-zakoni/zakon-o-dopuni-krivicnog-zakonika-republike-srpske>.

¹⁰⁵ "61st Report of the High Representative for Implementation of the Peace Agreement on Bosnia and Herzegovina to the Secretary-General of the United Nations," OHR, May 11, 2022, accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/61st-report-of-the-high-representative-for-implementation-of-the-peace-agreement-on-bosnia-and-herzegovina-to-the-secretary-general-of-the-united-nations/>.

¹⁰⁶ Hikmet Karčić, *Srebrenica Genocide Denial*, 61. First mentioned in note 88.

¹⁰⁷ See Constitutional Court of *Republika Srpska*, September 27, 2021, UV-2/21; Constitutional Court of *Republika Srpska*, September 27, 2021, UV-1/21.

¹⁰⁸ Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, July 14, 2022, U-15/21.

after World War II. Although recognized as sovereign, these countries were placed under supranational supervision, with international authorities often passing acts in the name of the states under supervision.

By invoking its previous case law, the Constitutional Court then specified that the High Representative, when adopting legislation, acts in the Bosnian legal order as a national authority and that, therefore, the imposed law banning genocide denial enjoys the same status as the legislation passed by the national Parliament. It consequently found that the law on non-application of the High Representative decision, passed by the National Assembly of *Republika Srpska*, violated Article III (3) (b) of the Bosnian Constitution, which states that entities have a positive constitutional obligation to harmonize their legislation with the Constitution and decisions adopted by state institutions, including laws passed by the High Representative. The Court further found a violation of the principle of the rule of law established by Article I (2) of the Bosnian Constitution, which implies a political system based on respect for the Constitution, laws, and other regulations by both citizens and holders of governmental power. As clarified by the Court, the laws imposed by the High Representative do not have a permanent character, but the only way for such legislation to cease to have an effect (or to be changed) is a new decision adopted by the Bosnian Parliament.

The involvement of the state-level Constitution Court in the memory war with the *Republika Srpska* shows that constitutional adjudication bodies may play an important role in restoring the rule of law against illiberal memory politics.¹⁰⁹ What remains uncertain is whether *Republika Srpska* will respect the Constitutional Court's decision by applying the genocide denial ban within its territory. The then entity's President (and now the Serb member of the country's tripartite presidency), Željka Cvijanović, promptly described the Court's ruling as "another in a series of political decisions adopted by this judicial institution."¹¹⁰ This was not, however, the first time that the Bosnian Constitutional Court has been involved in memory struggles and, in the past, the Serb-majority entity failed to respect the Constitutional Court's rulings (and, subsequently, the obligations under the Dayton Peace Accords and the Bosnian Constitution). For example, it has never observed the decisions proclaiming the unconstitutionality of *Republika Srpska Day*, which is celebrated on January 9. This holiday marks the date in 1992 when Bosnian Serbs proclaimed their own State in Bosnia and Herzegovina, a move that triggered the war of the 1990s. Bosnian Muslims and Bosnian Croats, consequently, perceive this date as the beginning of ethnic cleansing and war crimes committed against them, which then escalated into the crime of genocide. January 9 also coincides with St. Stephen's Day, a Serbian Orthodox Christian holiday. It was precisely this religious component that led the Bosnian Constitutional Court to declare in November 2015 the unconstitutionality of Article 3 b) of the entity's law on holidays establishing the *Republika Srpska Day*¹¹¹ as it found it discriminatory against non-Serbs living in the entity.¹¹² Following this decision, the authorities of *Republika Srpska* organized a referendum asking whether January 9 should continue to be celebrated as

¹⁰⁹ Carna Pistan, "Bosnia and Herzegovina: The Constitutional Court Protects the Rule of Law Against Illiberal Memory Politics." *IACL-AIDC Blog*, November 8, 2022, accessed February 16, 2023, <https://blog-iacl-aidc.org/new-blog-3/2022/11/8/bosnia-and-herzegovina-the-constitutional-court-protects-the-rule-of-law-against-illiberal-memory-politics>.

¹¹⁰ "Region: Cvijanović: Odluka Ustavnog suda BiH politička; Sudija Ćeman: Odluka važi od objavljivanja u Službenom glasniku [Region: Cvijanović: The Decision of the Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina is Political; Judge Ćeman: The Decision is Valid from its Publication in the Official Gazette], *Danas.rs*, July 14, 2022, accessed July 15, 2022, <https://www.danas.rs/svet/region/cvijanovic-odluka-ustavnog-suda-bih-politicka-sudija-ceman-odluka-vazi-od-objavljivanja-u-službenom-glasniku/>.

¹¹¹ *Zakon o praznicima Republike Srpske* (Law on Holidays of *Republika Srpska*) of 2007 (Law No. 01-583/07, March 30, 2007), accessed February 15, 2023, https://www.rgurs.org/uploads/laws/24_1.%20zakon%20o%20praznicima%20Republike%20Srpske.pdf.

¹¹² Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, November 26, 2015, U 3/13.

Republika Srpska Day and 99.79 percent of voters supported the holiday.¹¹³ The referendum was held in September 2016, despite the direct order from the Constitutional Court to suspend it,¹¹⁴ and was later declared unconstitutional.¹¹⁵ Then, in October 2016, the Serb-majority entity passed a new law on *Republika Srpska* Day, which declared January 9 as a secular holiday.¹¹⁶ The latter law was also declared unconstitutional in March 2019,¹¹⁷ but *Republika Srpska* authorities have ignored once again the ruling with the consequence that the holiday continues to be celebrated and observed within the entity.¹¹⁸

Another example of the state-level Constitutional Court's involvement in memory struggles dates back to March 2006, when it declared the unconstitutionality of *Republika Srpska*'s anthem *Bože pravde* (God of Justice; same as in Serbia), and the coat of arms (almost identical to the Serbian one) as both represented only the Serb community rather than all three constituent peoples.¹¹⁹ The failure of *Republika Srpska* to enforce the ruling within six months led the Court, in January 2007, to render ineffective Articles 2 and 3 of the entity's constitutional law on the flag, coat of arms, and anthem, which established the contested emblems and forbade their use.¹²⁰ In this case, a new anthem, *Moja Republika* (My Republic), and coat of arms (a neutral seal with the flag and the letters RS in Cyrillic) were adopted in July 2008. Svein Mønnesland notes, however, that not only the new anthem did not mention Bosnia and Herzegovina, but that the lyrics "We have no other land" indicate opposition to the common state.¹²¹

Concluding Remarks

Adopted in mid-2021 to facilitate reconciliation, the High Representative's decision to ban the denial of genocide and other war crimes in Bosnia and Herzegovina has triggered instead an internal memory war that culminated in the adoption of illiberal memory laws by *Republika Srpska* and required the intervention of the state-level Constitutional Court. As in the case of ICTY's decisions, it remains unrealistic to expect that externally imposed memory laws can foster reconciliation in a deeply divided society. This, however, does not mean that internationally imposed memory laws cannot help memorialization processes that promote a democratic culture and respect for human rights.¹²² The duty to adopt such memorialization policies in societies that have suffered gross violations of human rights derives from both primary and secondary sources of international human rights law.¹²³ While for example, the Durban Declaration of the World Conference against Racism, Racial Discrimination, Xenophobia, and Related Intolerance of 2001

¹¹³ Eleanor Rose, "Bosnian Serbs Defy State with Referendum Landslide," *Balkan Insight*, September 25, 2016, accessed February 22, 2022, <https://balkaninsight.com/2016/09/25/republika-srpska-referendum-early-results-09-25-2016/>.

¹¹⁴ Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, September 17, 2016, U 10/16.

¹¹⁵ Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, December 1, 2016, U 10/16.

¹¹⁶ *Zakon o danu Republike Srpske* (Law on *Republika Srpska* Day) of 2016 (Law No. 02/1-021-1239/16, October 25, 2016), (Rep. of Bosnia and Herzegovina), accessed February 22, 2023, <https://www.narodnaskupstinars.net/?q=la/akti/usvojeni-zakoni/zakon-o-danu-republike-srpske-0>.

¹¹⁷ Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, March 28, 2019, U 2/18.

¹¹⁸ See Azem Kurtic, "Armed Police and Bikers Parade as Bosnian Serbs Mark Banned Holiday," *Balkan Insight*, January 9, 2023, accessed February 24, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2023/01/09/armed-police-and-bikers-parade-as-bosnian-serbs-mark-banned-holiday/>.

¹¹⁹ Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, March 31, 2006, U 4/04.

¹²⁰ Constitutional Court of Bosnia and Herzegovina, January 27, 2007, U 4/04.

¹²¹ See Svein Mønnesland, *National Symbols in Multinational States: The Yugoslav Case* (Oslo: Syppress Forlag, 2013), 187.

¹²² In this sense, see also UN Human Rights Council, *Memorialization Processes: Report of the Special Rapporteur in the Field of Cultural Rights, Farida Shaheed*, January 23, 2014 (UN Doc. A/HRC/25/49), noting that external actors can play an important role in memorialization.

¹²³ See UN Human Rights Council, *Memorialization Processes in the Context of Serious Violations of Human Rights and International Humanitarian Law: The Fifth Pillar of Transitional Justice*, Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Promotion of Truth, Justice, Reparation and Guarantees of Non-Recurrence, July 9, 2020 (UN Doc. A/HRC/45/45).

defines memorialization as a tool for combating injustice and promoting peace,¹²⁴ the Updated Set of Principles for the protection and promotion of human rights through action to combat impunity of 2005, which formed the basis for the Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law of 2006,¹²⁵ establish that memorialization should respect the right to truth and reparation, and the guarantees of non-recurrence, as well as position the victims of violence as central.¹²⁶

In Bosnia and Herzegovina, the Office of the High Representative has played a crucial role in aligning memorialization to standards and criteria requested by international law. The main example of this is the commemoration of the Srebrenica massacre. The construction of the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery was, in fact, possible thanks to the decision imposed by the High Representative. Without his involvement, the Memorial Center may never have come into being as Srebrenica is located in *Republika Srpska*. Since its establishment in October 2000, the Memorial Center has served a symbolic purpose that has encouraged many Bosnian Muslim refugees to return to Srebrenica, thus reversing symbolically the results of ethnic cleansing and genocide committed in the war.¹²⁷ As far as the 2021 genocide denial ban is concerned, despite the tensions that have emerged following its imposition, it represents a much-needed law. Rather than reconciliation being a goal in itself, the law should be seen as a condition to make the process of reconciliation possible if and when political will becomes more inclined to achieve that goal. On the one hand, the law banning genocide denial protects and preserves the legal truth and the legacy of the ICTY, thus creating a source from which a more democratic memory construction could be initiated in the future. On the other hand, it provides a legal framework capable of combatting the deep institutional and social acceptance of a culture of denialism and triumphalism. In a democratic society, different interpretations of the past may coexist, but this should never result in genocide denial and glorification of war criminals. In Bosnia and Herzegovina, genocide denial humiliates victims and survivors, while the glorification of war criminals places perpetrators at the forefront rather than acknowledging the suffering of those who endured violence. By contrast, the 2021 law penalizing the denial of genocide and other international crimes is, as Western European punitive memory laws, an expression of a victim-centered culture of memory. It further supports the international obligation of the state to criminalize genocide denial. This obligation derives, for example, from the UN Human Rights Committee (a body of independent experts that monitors the implementation of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights of 1966), which stated that public denial of international crimes must be subject to criminal prosecution whether it constitutes incitement to violence and racial hatred, and the Genocide Convention, which further punishes direct and public incitement to commit genocide.¹²⁸

Yet it is true that in the years following the imposition of the genocide denial ban, Bosnian prosecutors have not filed any indictment on its basis primarily due to the difficulty in proving the existence of criminal offenses.¹²⁹ Despite this, both the 2022 and 2023 Srebrenica Genocide Denial Reports, published annually by the Memorial Center, show that there has been

¹²⁴ United Nations, *Durban Declaration and Plan of Action, Adopted at the World Conference Against Racism, Racial Discrimination, Xenophobia and Related Violence*, September 8, 2001.

¹²⁵ See UN Commission on Human Rights, *Updated Set of Principles for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights through Action to Combat Impunity*, February 8, 2005 (UN Doc. E/CN.4/2005/102/Add.1); United Nations, *General Assembly Resolution 60/147, Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law*, March 21, 2006 (UN Doc. A/RES/60/147).

¹²⁶ UN Human Rights Council, *Memorialization Processes* (UN Doc. A/HRC/45/45).

¹²⁷ See Duijzings, *Commemorating Srebrenica*, 146. First mentioned in note 71.

¹²⁸ See Fronza, *Memory and Punishment*, 51. First mentioned in note 23.

¹²⁹ See, for example, Lamija Grebo, "Bosnia's Genocide Denial Law: Why Prosecutors Haven't Charged Anyone," *Balkan Insight*, February 28, 2023, accessed March 3, 2023, <https://balkaninsight.com/2023/02/28/bosnias-genocide-denial-law-why-prosecutors-havent-charged-anyone/>.

a significant decline in the denial of Srebrenica Genocide in the public and media space, while the main deniers remain politicians and institutions in *Republika Srpska*.¹³⁰ The 2023 report suggests, in particular, that the criminal sanction established by the imposed legislation has played an important role in decreasing instances of denial. The same report further recommends international assistance in the judicial enforcement of the prohibition of denial, as outlined in the amendments to Bosnia's Criminal Code.

Author's Note

This publication is part of the project We-R (Illusions of Eternity: The Constitution as a Lieu de Mémoire and the Problem of Collective Remembrance in the Western Balkans) that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No. 898966.

Bibliography

- Al Jazeera. "What are the 10 Stages of Genocide?" July 10, 2020. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://www.aljazeera.com/amp/news/2020/7/10/what-are-the-10-stages-of-genocide>.
- Allcock, John B. "The International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia." In *Confronting the Yugoslav Controversies: A Scholars' Initiative*, edited by Charles Ingrao and Thomas A. Emmert, 347–389. West Lafayette: Purdue University Press, 2009.
- Appleton, Josie, Pierre Nora, and Olivier Salvatori. "Freedom for History? The Case Against Memory Laws." *Free Speech Debate*, April 3, 2013. Accessed February 26, 2023. <http://freespeechdebate.com/discuss/freedom-for-history-the-case-against-memory-laws/>.
- Arzt, Donna E. "Views on the Ground: The Local Perception of International Criminal Tribunals in the Former Yugoslavia and Sierra Leone." *Annals of the American Academy of Political and Social Science* 603, no. 1 (2006), 226–239.
- Assman, Aleida. "Europe: A Community of Memory?" *German Historical Institute Bulletin*, no. 40 (2007), 11–25.
- Bachmann, Klaus, Igor Lyubashenko, Christian Garuka, Grażyna Baranowska, and Vjieran Pavlaković. "The Puzzle of Punitive Memory Laws: New Insights into the Origins and Scope of Punitive Memory Laws." *East European Politics and Societies and Cultures* 35, no. 4 (2021), 996–1012.
- Baranowska, Grażyna, and Anna Wójcik. "In Defence of Europe's Memory Laws." *Eurozine*, November 6, 2017. Accessed April 25, 2024. <https://www.eurozine.com/in-defence-of-europes-memory-laws/>.
- BBC News. "Bosnia War Dead Figure Announced," June 21, 2007. Accessed January 24, 2023. <http://news.bbc.co.uk/2/hi/europe/6228152.stm>.
- Behrens, Paul. "Genocide Denial and the Law: A Critical Appraisal." *Buffalo Human Rights Law Review* 21, no. 1 (2015), 27–51.
- Belavusau, Uladzislau, and Aleksandra Gliszczyńska-Grabias. "Introduction: Mapping a New Subject in Comparative Law and Transitional Justice." In *Law and Memory: Towards Legal Governance of History*, edited by Uladzislau Belavusau and Aleksandra Gliszczyńska-Grabias, 12–37. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2017.
- Belavusau, Uladzislau, Aleksandra Gliszczyńska-Grabias, and Maria Mälksoo. "Memory Laws and Memory Wars in Poland, Russia and Ukraine." *Jahrbuch des öffentlichen Rechts* 69, no. 1 (2021), 95–116.

¹³⁰ Adem Mehmedović et al., *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2022* (Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, December 2022), 30, accessed March 3, 2023, https://srebrenicamemorial.org/assets/photos/editor/mcs_izvjestaj_ENG_2022_FINAL_DI.pdf; Muamer Džananović et al., *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2023* (Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, July 2023), accessed August 3, 2023, <https://srebrenicamemorial.org/bs/istrazivanja/srebrenica-genocide-denial-report-2023/18>.

- Bloomfield, David. "Reconciliation: An Introduction." In *Reconciliation After Violent Conflict: A Handbook*, edited by David Bloomfield, Teresa Barnes, and Luc Huyse, 10–18. Stockholm: International IDEA, 2003.
- Campbell, Kirsten. "The Laws of Memory: The ICTY, the Archive, and Transitional Justice." *Social & Legal Studies* 22, no. 2 (2013), 247–269.
- Cassese, Antonio. "Reflections on International Criminal Justice." *Modern Law Review* 61, no. 1 (1998), 1–10.
- Clark, Janine. *International Trials and Reconciliation: Assessing the Impact of the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia*. New York City: Routledge, 2015.
- Council of Europe. *Additional Protocol to the Convention on Cybercrime, Concerning the Criminalisation of Acts of a Racist and Xenophobic Nature Committed through Computer Systems* (European Treaty Series—No. 189), January 28, 2003. Accessed February 25, 2023. <https://rm.coe.int/168008160f>.
- . "Memory Laws" and Freedom of Expression. Strasbourg: Council of Europe, July 2018. Accessed January 20, 2023. <https://rm.coe.int/factsheet-on-memory-laws-july2018-docx/16808c1690>.
- Danas.rs. "Cvijanović: Odluka Ustavnog suda BiH politička; Sudija Čeman: Odluka važi od objavljivanja u Službenom glasniku." July 15, 2022. Accessed July 15, 2022. <https://www.danas.rs/svet/region/cvijanovic-odluka-ustavnog-suda-bih-politicka-sudija-čeman-odluka-vazi-od-objavljivanja-u-sluzbenom-glasniku/>.
- Dragović-Soso, Jasna. "Apologising for Srebrenica: The Declaration of the Serbian Parliament, the European Union and the Politics of Compromise." *East European Politics* 28, no. 2 (2012), 163–179.
- Duijzings, Ger. "Commemorating Srebrenica: Histories of Violence and the Politics of Memory in Eastern Bosnia." In *The New Bosnian Mosaic: Identities, Memories and Moral Claims in a Post-War Society*, edited by Xavier Bougarel, Elissa Helms, and Ger Duijzings, 141–166. Burlington: Ashgate Publishing, 2007.
- Dzaferagic, Nejra. "Bosnia Under Pressure to Adopt Srebrenica Genocide Denial Law." *Balkan Insight*, April 16, 2021. Accessed January 21, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2021/04/16/bosnia-under-pressure-to-adopt-srebrenica-genocide-denial-law/>.
- Dzaferovic, Nejra. "Bosnian Streets and Squares Named After War Criminals." *Balkan Insight*, May 19, 2020. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2020/05/19/bosnian-streets-and-squares-named-after-war-criminals/>.
- Džananović, Muamer, Adem Mehmedović, Nikola Vučić, and Edin Ikanović. *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2023*. Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, July 2023. Accessed August 3, 2023. <https://srebrenicamemorial.org/bs/istrazivanje/srebrenica-genocide-denial-report-2023/18>.
- European Commission. *Commission Staff Working Document: Bosnia and Herzegovina 2020 Report*. Brussels: European Commission, October 6, 2020. Accessed February 6, 2023. https://neighbourhood-enlargement.ec.europa.eu/system/files/2020-10/bosnia_and_herzegovina_report_2020.pdf.
- European Union. *Council Framework Decision 2008/913/JHA of 28 November 2008 on Combating Certain Forms and Expressions of Racism and Xenophobia by Means of Criminal Law*. November 28, 2008. 2008/913/JHA. Accessed February 25, 2023. https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dec_framw/2008/913/oj.
- Fisher, Martina. "Transitional Justice and Reconciliation: Theory and Practice." In *Advancing Conflict Transformation: The Berghof Handbook II*, edited by Beatrix Austin, Martina Fisher, and Hans J. Giessmann, 405–430. Opladen: Barbara Budrich, 2011.
- Fletcher, Laurel E., and Harvey M. Weinstein. "A World Unto Itself? The Application of International Justice in the Former Yugoslavia." In *My Neighbor, My Enemy: Justice and Community in the Aftermath of Mass Atrocity*, edited by Eric Stover and Harvey M. Weinstein, 29–48. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2004.

- Fronza, Emanuela. *Memory and Punishment: Historical Denialism, Free Speech and the Limits of Criminal Law*. The Hague: T.M.C. Asser Press, 2018.
- Gaćanica, Lejla, and Caroline Finkeldey. *Calling War Atrocities by their Right Name: Regulating a Ban on Denial, Trivialisation, Justification or Condonation of Genocide, the Holocaust, Crimes against Humanity or War Crimes*. Sarajevo: Forum Ziviler Friedensdienst—TRIAL International, 2019. <https://trialinternational.org/wp-content/uploads/2020/02/Calling-War-Atrocities-by-their-Right-Name-TRIAL-ZFD-EN-2019.pdf>.
- Gliszczyńska-Grabias, Aleksandra. "Penalizing Holocaust Denial: A View from Europe." In *Global Antisemitism: A Crisis of Modernity*, edited by Charles Asher Small, 237–256. Leiden: Martinus Nijhoff Publishers, 2013.
- Grebo, Lamija. "Bosnia's Genocide Denial Law: Why Prosecutors Haven't Charged Anyone." *Balkan Insight*, February 28, 2023. Accessed March 3, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2023/02/28/bosnias-genocide-denial-law-why-prosecutors-havent-charged-anyone/>.
- Green, Monica Hanson. *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2020*. Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, May 2020. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://weremember.gov.tr/documents/Srebrenica-Genocide-Denial-Report-min.pdf>.
- Halilovich, Hariz. "25 Years After Srebrenica: 'Local' Genocide in a Global Context." In *Bosnian Genocide Denial and Triumphalism: Origins, Impact and Prevention*, edited by Sead Turčalo and Hikmet Karčić, 115–125. Sarajevo: University of Sarajevo, 2021.
- Haysom, Nicholas. "Constitution Making and Nation Building." In *Federalism in a Changing World: Learning from Each Other*, edited by Raoul Blindenbacher and Arnold Koller, 216–239. London: McGill-Queen's University Press, 2003.
- Helsinki Watch. *War Crimes in Bosnia-Herzegovina: Vol. II*. USA: Human Rights Watch, 1992. Accessed January 22, 2023. <https://www.hrw.org/reports/pdfs/y/yugoslav/yugo.928/yugo928full.pdf>.
- Hronešová, Jessie Barton, and Jasmin Hasić. "The 2021 Memory Law in Bosnia and Herzegovina—Reconciliation or Polarization?" *Journal of Genocide Research* (2003), 1–19.
- Huyse, Luc. "Introduction: Tradition-Based Approaches in Peacemaking, Transitional Justice and Reconciliation Policies." In *Traditional Justice and Reconciliation After Violent Conflict: Learning from African Experiences*, edited by Luc Huyse and Mark Salter, 1–24. Stockholm: International IDEA, 2008.
- . "Justice After Transition: On the Choices Successor Elites Make in Dealing with the Past." *Law & Social Inquiry* 20, no. 1 (1995), 51–78.
- . "The Process of Reconciliation." In *Reconciliation after Violent Conflict. A Handbook*, edited by David Bloomfield, Teresa Barnes, and Luc Huyse, 19–34. Stockholm: International IDEA, 2005.
- Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Sufferings of all People in the Srebrenica Region Between 1992 and 1995. *Concluding Report of the Independent International Commission of Inquiry on Suffering of All People in the Srebrenica Region Between 1992 and 1995*. July 21, 2021. Accessed March 20, 2023. <https://incomfis-srebrenica.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/07/Srebrenica%20Commission%20report%20-%20English%20lan.pdf>.
- Jorda, Claude. "The ICTY and the Truth and Reconciliation Commission in Bosnia and Herzegovina." Speech, Sarajevo, May 12, 2001. United Nations, International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia. Accessed January 20, 2023. <https://www.icty.org/en/press/icty-and-truth-and-reconciliation-commission-bosnia-and-herzegovina>.
- Judt, Tony. *Postwar: A History of Europe Since 1945*. New York: The Penguin Press, 2005.
- Karčić, Hamza. "Analysis: What Bosnia's New Genocide Denial Ban Means." *Anadolu Agency*, July 27, 2021. Accessed February 7, 2023. <https://www.aa.com.tr/en/analysis/analysis-what-bosnias-new-genocide-denial-ban-means/2315421>.
- Karčić, Hikmet. "Srebrenica Genocide Denial: From Dodik to TikTok." In *Bosnian Genocide Denial and Triumphalism: Origins, Impact and Prevention*, edited by Sead Turčalo and Hikmet Karčić, 60–63. Sarajevo: University of Sarajevo, 2021.

- Koposov, Nikolay. *Memory Laws, Memory Wars: The Politics of the Past in Europe and Russia*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2018.
- . "Populism and Memory: Legislation of the Past in Poland, Ukraine, and Russia." *East European Politics and Societies and Cultures* 36, no. 1 (2022), 272–297.
- Kostić, Roland. *Reconciling the Past and the Present: Evaluating the Dayton Peace Agreement 1995*. Uppsala: Uppsala University Press, 2009.
- Kovacevic, Danijel. "Bosnian Serbs Reject Call to Revoke War Criminals' Honours." *Balkan Insight*, May 12, 2021. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2021/05/12/bosnian-serbs-reject-call-to-revoke-war-criminals-honours/>.
- Kuloglija, Nermina, and Azra Husaric Omerovic. "Bosnian Genocide Denial Ban Pleases Survivors, Angers Serbs." *Balkan Insight*, July 23, 2021. Accessed February 15, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2021/07/23/bosnian-genocide-denial-ban-pleases-survivors-angers-serbs/>.
- Kurtic, Azem. "Armed Police and Bikers Parade as Bosnian Serbs Mark Banned Holiday." *Balkan Insight*, January 9, 2023. Accessed February 24, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2023/01/09/armed-police-and-bikers-parade-as-bosnian-serbs-mark-banned-holiday/>.
- Ledoux, Sébastien. "Memory laws in Europe: What Common Horizons are we Journeying Towards?" *Magazine of the European Observatory on Memories*, March 11, 2022. Accessed January 20, 2023. <https://europeanmemories.net/magazine/memory-laws-in-europe-what-common-horizons-are-we-journeying-towards/>.
- Lobba, Paolo. "Holocaust Denial before the European Court of Human Rights: Evolution of an Exceptional Regime," *European Journal of International Law* 26, no. 1 (2015), 237–253.
- Loi No. 90-615 du 13 juillet 1990 tendant à réprimer tout acte raciste, antisémite ou xénophobe (Law No. 90-615 of 13 July 1990 Tending to Repress Any Racist, anti-Semitic or Xenophobic acts) of 1990 (Law No. 90-615), July 13, 1990. (Rep. of France). Accessed February 10, 2023. <https://www.legifrance.gouv.fr/loda/id/JORFTEXT000000532990>.
- Meernik, James. "Justice and Peace? How the International Criminal Tribunal Affects Societal Peace in Bosnia." *Journal of Peace Research* 42, no. 3 (2005), 271–289.
- Mehmedović, Adem, Kadira Šakić, Edin Ikanović, and Nikola Vučić. *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2022*. Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, December 2022. Accessed March 3, 2023. https://srebrenicamemorial.org/assets/photos/editor/mcs_izvjestaj_ENG_2022_FINAL_DI.pdf.
- Mehmedović, Adem, Kadira Šakić, and Tijana Cvjetičanin. *Srebrenica Genocide Denial Report 2021*. Srebrenica: The Srebrenica Memorial, June 2021. Accessed February 17, 2023. <https://srebrenicamemorial.org/assets/files/1625819683-srebrenica-genocide-denial-report-2021-english-language.pdf>.
- Memorial Center Srebrenica. "Genocide in Srebrenica." Accessed January 19, 2023. <https://srebrenicamemorial.org/en/page/genocide-in-srebrenica/26>.
- Mønnesland, Svein. *National Symbols in Multinational States: The Yugoslav Case*. Oslo: Syppress Forlag, 2013.
- N1. "Sarajevo, Dodik Names Inzko's Decision on Genocide Denial the 'Last Nail in BiH's Coffin'." July 23, 2021. Accessed July 23, 2022. <https://ba.n1info.com/english/news/dodik-names-inzkos-decision-on-genocide-denial-the-last-nail-in-bihs-coffin>.
- Nettelfield, Lara J., and Sarah E. Wagner. *Srebrenica in the Aftermath of Genocide*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2014.
- Office of the High Representative (OHR). "61st Report of the High Representative for Implementation of the Peace Agreement on Bosnia and Herzegovina to the Secretary-General of the United Nations." May 11, 2022. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/61st-report-of-the-high-representative-for-implementation-of-the-peace-agreement-on-bosnia-and-herzegovina-to-the-secretary-general-of-the-united-nations/>.
- . "Decision Amending the Federation Law on Preservation of Assets Declared National Monuments of BiH Under Decisions of the Commission for Protection of National Monuments of 2002." August 2, 2002. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/>

- [decision-amending-the-federation-law-on-preservation-of-assets-declared-national-monuments-of-bih-under-decisions-of-the-commission-for-protection-of-national-monuments/](#).
- . “Decision Enacting Amendments to the Constitution of the Federation of Bosnia and Herzegovina: 06/22.” October 2, 2022. Accessed January 28, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-amendments-to-the-constitution-of-the-federation-of-bosnia-and-herzegovina-3/>.
- . “Decision Enacting the Law on Amendments to the Election Law of Bosnia and Herzegovina: 07/22.” October 2, 2022. Accessed January 28, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-the-law-on-amendments-to-the-election-law-of-bosnia-and-herzegovina-8/>.
- . “Decision Enacting the Law on Amendments to the Law on the Center for the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery for the Victims of the 1995 Genocide.” February 21, 2023. Accessed March 13, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-the-law-on-amendments-to-the-law-on-the-center-for-the-srebrenica-potocari-memorial-and-cemetery-for-the-victims-of-the-1995-genocide-2/>.
- . “Decision Enacting the Law on the Center for the Srebrenica-Potocari Memorial and Cemetery for the Victims of the 1995 Genocide.” June 25, 2007. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-enacting-the-law-on-the-center-for-the-srebrenica-potocari-memorial-and-cemetery-for-the-victims-of-the-1995-genocide/>.
- . “Decision Establishing and Registering the Foundation of the Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial and Cemetery.” May 10, 2001. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-establishing-and-registering-the-foundation-of-the-srebrenica-potocari-memorial-and-cemetery/>.
- . “Decision Imposing the Law on the Flag of BiH.” February 4, 1998. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-imposing-the-law-on-the-flag-of-bih/>.
- . “Decision Imposing the Law on the National Anthem of BiH.” June 25, 1999. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-imposing-the-law-on-the-national-anthem-of-bih/>.
- . Decision Imposing the RS Law on Implementation of Decisions of the Commission to Preserve National Monuments Established under Annex 8 of the Dayton Peace Agreement.” August 2, 2002. Accessed January 21, 2023, <http://www.ohr.int/decision-imposing-the-rs-law-on-implementation-of-decisions-of-the-commission-to-preserve-national-monuments-established-under-annex-8-of-the-dayton-peace-agreement/>.
- . “Decision on the Location of a Cemetery and a Monument for the Victims of Srebrenica.” October 25, 2000. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-on-the-location-of-a-cemetery-and-a-monument-for-the-victims-of-srebrenica/>.
- . “Decision on the Shape and Design of the Coat-of-Arms of BiH.” May 18, 1998. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/decision-on-the-shape-and-design-of-the-coat-of-arms-of-bih/>.
- . “High Representative Enables Better Functioning of Srebrenica-Potočari Memorial Center.” Press Release, Sarajevo, February 21, 2022. Accessed March 13, 2023. www.ohr.int/high-representative-valentin-inzko-introduced-today-amendment-to-the-bh-criminal-code/.
- . “High Representative Valentin Inzko Introduced Today Amendments to the BH Criminal Code: Forgiveness and Reconciliation are Most Important.” Press Release, Sarajevo, July 23, 2021. Accessed February 3, 2023. www.ohr.int/high-representative-valentin-inzko-introduced-today-amendment-to-the-bh-criminal-code/.
- . “HR’s Decision on Enacting the Law on Amendment to the Criminal Code of Bosnia and Herzegovina.” July 23, 2021. Accessed January 21, 2023. <http://www.ohr.int/hrs-decision-on-enacting-the-law-on-amendment-to-the-criminal-code-of-bosnia-and-herzegovina>.

- Orentlicher, Diane F. *That Someone Guilty Be Punished: The Impact of the ICTY in Bosnia*. New York: Open Society Justice Initiative, 2010.
- Osiel, Mark J. *Mass Atrocity, Collective Memory, and the Law*. New Brunswick: Transaction Publishers, 1997.
- Pankhurst, Donna. "Issues of Justice and Reconciliation in Complex Political Emergencies: Conceptualising Reconciliation, Justice and Peace." *Third World Quarterly* 20, no. 1 (1999), 239–256.
- Pech, Laurent. "The Law of Holocaust Denial in Europe: Towards a (Qualified) EU-Wide Criminal Prohibition." *Jean Monnet Working Paper 10/09* (New York: NYU School of Law, 2009).
- Perrin, Kristen. "Memory at the International Criminal Tribunal for the Former Yugoslavia (ICTY): Discussions on Remembering and Forgetting within Victim Testimonies." *East European Politics and Societies and Cultures* 30, no. 2 (2016), 270–287.
- Petó, Andrea. "The Illiberal Memory Politics in Hungary." *Journal of Genocide Research* 24, no. 2 (2022), 241–249.
- Pistan, Carna. "Alarming Alterations: How Memory Politics Turned the Russian Constitution into a War Weapon." PONARS Eurasia Policy Memo No. 798, George Washington University, September 26, 2022. Accessed February 26, 2023. <https://www.ponarseurasia.org/alarming-alterations-how-memory-politics-turned-the-russian-constitution-into-a-war-weapon/>.
- . "Bosnia and Herzegovina: The Constitutional Court Protects the Rule of Law Against Illiberal Memory Politics." *IACL-AIDC Blog*, November 8, 2022. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://blog-iacl-aidc.org/new-blog-3/2022/11/8/bosnia-and-herzegovina-the-constitutional-court-protects-the-rule-of-law-against-illiberal-memory-politics>.
- . "Call it by its Right Name: Criminalizing Genocide Denial in Bosnia and Herzegovina." *Verfassungsblog*, August 23, 2021. Accessed February 7, 2023. <https://verfassungsblog.de/call-it-by-its-right-name/>.
- Rahim, Zamira. "Srebrenica Massacre is 'Fabricated Myth', Bosnian Serb Leader Says." *Independent*, April 14, 2019. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://www.independent.co.uk/news/world/europe/srebrenica-massacre-genocide-milorad-dodik-bosnia-myth-a8869026.html>.
- Rose, Eleanor. "Bosnian Serbs Defy State with Referendum Landslide." *Balkan Insight*, September 25, 2016. Accessed February 22, 2022. <https://balkaninsight.com/2016/09/25/republika-srpska-referendum-early-results-09-25-2016/>.
- Rosensaft, Menachem Z. "Deceptive Report Escalates Srebrenica Genocide Denial Campaign." *Just Security*, July 29, 2021. Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://www.justsecurity.org/77628/deceptive-report-escalates-srebrenica-genocide-denial-campaign/>.
- Šarić, Sabahudin. "The Denial of Genocide in Srebrenica in the Context of Strengthening Neo-fascism and Relativization of the Holocaust in Europe." *Bosnian Studies* V, no. 1 (2021), 65–81.
- Schaap, Andrew. "The Time of Reconciliation and the Space for Politics." In *Law and the Politics of Reconciliation*, edited by Scott Veitch, 9–32. London: Routledge, 2007.
- Seils, Paul. "The Place of Reconciliation in Transitional Justice." ICTJ briefing, June 2017. Accessed March 20, 2023, <https://www.ictj.org/publication/reconciliation-transitional-justice>.
- Sierp, Aline. "Integrating Europe, Integrating Memories: The EU's Politics of Memory Since 1945." In *The Transcultural Turn: Interrogating Memory Between and Beyond Borders*, edited by Lucy Bond and Jessica Rapson, 103–118. Berlin: De Gruyter, 2014.
- Smith, Roger W. "Legislating Against Genocide Denial: Criminalizing Denial or Preventing Free Speech?" *University of St. Thomas Journal of Law and Public Policy* 4, no. 2 (2010), 128–137.
- Snyman, Johannes. "Interpretation and the Politics of Memory." *Acta Juridica*, no. 8 (1998), 312–321.
- Sokol, Anida. "War Monuments: Instruments of Nation-Building in Bosnia and Herzegovina." *Croatian Political Science Review* 51, no. 5 (2014), 105–126.
- Soroka, George, and Krawatzek, Félix. "Nationalism, Democracy, and Memory Laws." *Journal of Democracy* 30, no. 2 (2019), 157–171.

- Spaic, Igor. "Srebrenica's Serb Mayor Repeats Denial of Genocide." *Balkan Insight*, April 13, 2017. Accessed February 15, 2023. <https://balkaninsight.com/2017/04/13/srebrenica-s-serb-mayor-repeats-denial-of-genocide-04-13-2017/>.
- Stanton, Gregory H. "Ten Stages of Genocide." *Genocide Watch*. Accessed February 17, 2023. <https://www.genocidewatch.com/tenstages>.
- Subotic, Jelena. "Remembrance, Public Narratives, and Obstacles to Justice in the Western Balkans." *Studies in Social Justice* 7, no. 2 (2013), 265–283.
- Tate, Jahnisa. "Turkey's Article 301: A Legitimate Tool for Maintaining Order or a Threat to Freedom of Expression." *Georgia Journal of International and Comparative Law* 37, no. 1 (2008), 181–217.
- Trahan, Jennifer. "Examining the Benchmarks by which to Evaluate the ICTY's Legacy." In *Bosnian Genocide Denial and Triumphalism: Origins, Impact and Prevention*, edited by Sead Turčalo and Hikmet Karčić, 64–89. Sarajevo: University of Sarajevo, 2021.
- UN Commission on Human Rights. *Updated Set of Principles for the Protection and Promotion of Human Rights through Action to Combat Impunity*. February 8, 2005. UN Doc. E/CN.4/2005/102/Add.1.
- UN Human Rights Council. *Memorialization Processes in the Context of Serious Violations of Human Rights and International Humanitarian Law: The Fifth Pillar of Transitional Justice, Report of the Special Rapporteur on the Promotion of Truth, Justice, Reparation and Guarantees of Non-Recurrence*. July 9, 2020. UN Doc. A/HRC/45/45.
- . *Memorialization Processes: Report of the Special Rapporteur in the Field of Cultural Rights, Farida Shaheed*. January 23, 2014. UN Doc. A/HRC/25/49.
- United Nations. *Durban Declaration and Plan of Action, Adopted at the World Conference Against Racism, Racial Discrimination, Xenophobia and Related Violence*. September 8, 2001.
- . *General Assembly Resolution 60/147, Basic Principles and Guidelines on the Right to a Remedy and Reparation for Victims of Gross Violations of International Human Rights Law and Serious Violations of International Humanitarian Law*. March 21, 2006. UN Doc. A/RES/60/147.
- . *Security Council Resolution 1534*, March 26, 2004. UN Doc. S/RES/1534 (2004).
- Vermeersch, Peter. "Victimhood as Victory: The Role of Memory Politics in the Process of de-Europeanization in East Central Europe." *Global Discourse: An Interdisciplinary Journal of Current Affairs* 9, no. 1 (2019), 113–130.
- Vukušić, Iva. "Archives of Mass Violence: Understanding and Using ICTY Trial Records." *Comparative Southeast European Studies* 70, no. 4 (2022), 585–607.
- Williams, Paul R., and Michael P. Scharf. *Peace with Justice? War Crimes and Accountability in the Former Yugoslavia*. Lanham: Rowman & Littlefield Publishers, 2002.
- Zakon o danu Republike Srpske* (Law on Republika Srpska Day) of 2016 (Law No. 02/1-021-1239/16, October 25, 2016). (Republika Srpska). Accessed February 22, 2023. <https://www.narodnaskupstinars.net/?q=la/akti/usvojeni-zakoni/zakon-o-danu-republike-srpske-0>.
- Zakon o dopuni Krivičnog zakonika Republike Srpske* (Law on Amendments to the Criminal Code of Republika Srpska) of 2021 (Law No. 02/1-021-586/21, July 30, 2021). (Republika Srpska). Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://www.narodnaskupstinars.net/?q=la/akti/usvojeni-zakoni/zakon-o-dopuni-krivicnog-zakonika-republike-srpske>.
- Zakon o neprimjenjivanju Odluke Visokog predstavnika kojom se donosi Zakon o dopuni Krivičnog zakona Bosne i Hercegovine* (Law on Non-Applicability of the Decision the High Representative Enacting the Law on Amendment to the Criminal Code of Bosnia and Herzegovina) of 2021 (Law No. 02/1-021-584/21, July 30, 2021). (Republika Srpska). Accessed February 16, 2023. <https://www.narodnaskupstinars.net/?q=la/akti/usvojeni-zakoni/zakon-o-neprimjenjivanju-odluke-visokog-predstavnika-kojom-se-donosi-zakon-o-dopuni-krivicnog-zakona-bosne-i-hercegovine>.
- Zakon o praznicima Republike Srpske* (Law on Holidays of Republika Srpska) of 2007 (Law No. 01-583/07, March 30, 2007). (Republika Srpska). Accessed February 15, 2023. <https://www.rgurs.org/uploads/laws/24.1.%20zakon%20o%20praznicima%20Republike%20Srpske.pdf>.